

**European Forum on Urban Forestry –
Zürich 04. June – 07. June 2025**

Urban Forests for Resilient and Healthy Cities

About EFUF: The European Forum on Urban Forestry (EFUF) is a meeting place for practitioners, policymakers, managers, educators and scientists who are active in urban forestry, urban greening and green infrastructure. Founded in 1998, EFUF meets annually to discuss new developments, to exchange experiences, and to visit examples of good practices on planning, design and management of urban forests (from woodland to urban parks and street trees). Participants come from across Europe, as well as from other parts of the world. EFUF is associated with the International Union of Forest Research Organisations' (IUFRO Division 6.07.00 – Urban forestry) urban forestry group, as well as with several European and Nordic networks for urban forestry.

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URBAN FORESTS FOR RESILIENT AND HEALTHY CITIES

27TH EUROPEAN FORUM ON URBAN FORESTRY (EFUF 2025)

3rd -7th June 2025, Zurich, Switzerland

Book of Abstract

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WELCOME TO THE 27TH EUROPEAN FORUM ON URBAN FORESTRY

Cities around the world are increasingly challenged by the impacts of climate change. Rising temperatures, more frequent heatwaves and prolonged droughts demand effective and sustainable solutions to protect urban quality of life and strengthen of ecological resilience. In this context, the urban forest plays a vital role.

Urban forests - from individual street trees to expansive forests within or around cities – are much more than just design elements in urban spaces. They offer shade, cool the air through evaporation, filter pollutants, support biodiversity by providing habitat for countless species and contribute significantly to a healthier urban microclimate. Their benefits for both the environment and public health are indispensable.

Yet in densely built cities, preserving and expanding the urban tree canopy is challenging. Limited space, competing land uses, underground infrastructure, and shifting climatic conditions all present significant obstacles to planting and maintenance. That’s why it’s more important than ever to integrate urban forest into city planning through the lens of urban forestry – guided by innovative strategies, clear objectives, actionable plans, and, above all, a strong commitment to knowledge sharing.

A resilient, diverse, and thriving urban forest doesn’t happen by chance. It requires thoughtful planning, collaboration between the public sector, private landowners, researchers and civil society, and a shared recognition of nature as an essential urban asset. Only when all stakeholders take responsibility can we succeed in shaping cities that are resilient, liveable, healthy and sustainable.

The European Forum on Urban Forestry serves as a platform to advance these shared goals. It is an opportunity to raise awareness of the value of urban forests, explore new pathways for action, and inspire concrete steps towards greener, healthier, resilient and sustainable cities.

We are very happy to welcome you to the European Forum on Urban Forestry in Zurich and wish you fantastic days and inspiring conversations paired with beautiful and fun moments within the Urban Forestry family.

We are looking forward to inspiring and fun days.

Prof. Dr. Jerylee Wilkes-Allemann
Professor of Forest and
Environmental Policy
Bern University of Applied Sciences,
School of Agricultural, Forest and
Food Sciences HAFL

Andrea Gion Saluz
Head Urban Trees Planning
Grün Stadt Zürich

Reto Mohr
Division Manager Forest,
Agriculture, Leases, Grün Stadt
Zürich

PROGRAMME

DAY 0 | Tuesday 3rd June 2025

Until 17.30 Travel to Zurich
 18.00-19.00 Welcome aperitive and icebreaker (Place: Stadtgärtnerei, Sackzelg 27, 8047 Zürich)

DAY 1 | Wednesday 4th June 2025

8.00	Registration at HG E 30.0065				Conference Room: HG G 3
8.30	Welcome to EFUF 2025 and Integrate Network by Jerylee Wilkes-Allemann (Bern University of Applied Sciences and ArboCityNet) Jonathan Spazzi (Integrate Network)				
8.40	Welcome by Christine Bräm and Andrea Saluz (Grün Stadt Zürich)				
8.50	Keynotes for conference theme 1: “Resilient and healthy environments: Challenges and opportunities between urban forestry and close-to-nature forestry” – Chair: Clive Davies (EFUF & M2D Consulting) Keynote 1 “EU scale, long term effects of integrated and adaptive forest management on Europe’s forests and its forest industry” – Gert-Jan Nabuurs (Wageningen University and Research) Keynote 2 “To re-wild or not - is this the question?” - Harald Bugmann (ETH Zurich)				
10.10	Coffee and tea break – networking				Room: HG E 4
10.40	Keynote 3 “Professional Credentials for Those Working in our Urban Forests” -Caitlyn Pollihan (International Society of Arboriculture) Keynote 4 “Effects of urban greenspaces on public health: serial mediation model of objective and subjective measures” -Wendy Chen (Urban Forestry and Urban Greening Journal)				
12.00	Take-home message Integrate Network by Frank Krumm (Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research) and Andreas Rigling (ETH Zurich)				
12.05	Ápero Riche				Room: HG E 4
13.00	Optional activities EFUF General Assembly and open meeting	Workshop 1 “35-minute movie about the “Grünes Gallustal” initiative with Florim Shabani (Verein Grünes Gallustal)	Workshop 2 “Informed Decisions, Effective Action: Credible Outcome Metrics for Urban Forestry” with Daniel Griswold (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe)	Workshop 3 “Launch SPOOL journal Special Issue ‘Urban Forest-scapes’ with René van der Velde (University of Technology Delft)	
14.00	Study visit to “Waldlabor” by Martin Brüllbardt (Waldlabor)				
19.30	Barbecue party in the forest and speed dating activities				

DAY 2 | Thursday 5th 2025

8.00 Registration at HG E 30.0065 Conference Room: HG G 3

8.30 Keynotes for conference theme 2:
“Creating healthy, resilient, safe and equitable urban environments: the potential of urban forests and participation” – Chair: Cecil Konijnendijk (Nature Based Solutions Institute)
 Keynote 5 “Radical Community Engagement: A practical approach to intersectional environmental justice in urban forestry” -Lotte Dijkstra (Newcastle University)
 Keynote 6 “Green Inequality and the Critical Role of Urban Forests in Advancing Social Integration in African Cities” -Ayanda Roji (Johannesburg City Parks and Zoo & Centre on African Public Spaces)
 Keynote 7 “Gender, fear and danger in dense and open urban forests” - Anna Bornioli (Barcelona Institute for Global Health)

10.00 Coffee and tea break – networking Room: HG E 4

<p>10.30 Parallel Sessions</p> <p>Session 1 - Urban Forests for Resilient Cities Chair: Daniel Griswold (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe) Room: HG G 26.1</p> <p>Eugènia Vidal-Casanovas “Greening the urban edge towards climate neutrality and resilience. The metropolitan area of Barcelona participation in the Horizon Commit2Green project.”</p> <p>Saskia de Wit “A tree language for Rotterdam. Guiding principles for a creative management culture”</p> <p>Glenn Fischer “Aesculus - quo vadis?”</p>	<p>Session 2 - Urban Forests for Healthy Cities Chair: Jean-Laurent Pfund (Pfund Consulting) Room: HG G 26.3</p> <p>Kelly Wittemans “LiDAR-based Assessment of Urban Tree Benefits from a OneHealth perspective”</p> <p>Christoph Bachofen “High transpiration cooling by urban trees despite extreme summer heatwaves”</p> <p>Leónia Nunes “The perception of public green spaces in Portugal with the focus on Lisbon”</p> <p>Arne Arnberger “Effects of school indoor environments</p>	<p>Session 3 - Urban Forests for Inclusive Cities Chair: Eva Lieberherr (ETH Zurich) Room: HG G 26.5</p> <p>Stijn Bruggen “A Methodology to Identify and Prioritize Tree Planting Locations in Urban Areas according to the 3-30-300 rule.”</p> <p>Jiawei Zhao “Rethinking Urban Green Space Accessibility Through Route Environment Quality”</p> <p>Jennifer Schulz “Urban Forest Gardens as a new form of co-</p>	<p>Session 4 - Urban Forests for Sustainable Urban Planning Chair: Barbara Darr (Weihenstephan-Triesdorf University of Applied Sciences) Room: HG F 33.5</p> <p>Stefan Stevanovic & Michael Richter “Challenges and Solutions in Measuring Urban Trees in the City Environment”</p> <p>Ana Paula Ramos “Management Strategies for Urban Trees in Lisbon: Addressing Decay Fungi and Enhancing Urban Tree Health”</p> <p>Philip Chambers “Transforming Urban Forest Monitoring through Gamified Augmented Reality”</p> <p>Sophie Emberger “Investigating the</p>
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<p>Apurva Malik “Unravelling Adaptive Resilience, Tolerance Mechanisms, and Mitigation Potential of Roadside Tree Species to Vehicular Emissions across Urban Habitats”</p>	<p>and green spaces on mental health of adolescent pupils: A crossover experiment”</p> <p>Nayanesh Pattnaik “Tree Performance and Cooling Benefits in Multi-layered Urban Forests”</p>	<p>created and co-managed urban forests”</p> <p>Eric Kramer “Data Driven Design: Systematic Approaches to Urban Forest Planning”</p>	<p>Water Sources of Urban Trees”</p> <p>Eric Amponsah “Greening Ejisu: Urban Forests for Sustainable Cities”</p>
<p>Martin Tušar “Bigger Roots, Stronger Cities: Rethinking Tree Watering for Climate Resilience”</p>	<p>Giorgia Burbui “Green areas and mortality: a health impact assessment in the Florentine plain”</p>	<p>Deanne Brettle “Urban forestry citizen science and community-based stewardship in Birmingham - the UK’s second largest city.”</p>	<p>Yakir Preisler “First results from the Urban Trees Ecophysiology Network (UTEN)”</p> <p>John Jose “Rewilding cities for climate and ecological resilience: a comparative study of Delhi and Milan”</p>
<p>Federica di Cagno & Cecil Konijnendijk “Strengthening the business case for urban forests”</p>	<p>Leandra Kausch “Differential Immune Modulation Following Short-Term Exposure to Two Forest Types Compared to an Urban Environment”</p>	<p>Alanis Camichel “Challenges and enabling factors of participation in the transition process towards a BioCity: learnings from Switzerland”</p>	
<p>Isaac Lievevrouw “Greening Cities, Growing Value: How PEFC Trees Outside Forests Certification Transforms Urban Forestry in the Netherlands”</p>		<p>Valentine Opanga “From Community to Commodity: Contestations over Space in the Making of Somali Enclaves in Nairobi’s Pumwani-Majengo”</p>	

12.15 Ápero Riche

Room: HG E 4

13.45 Flash posters presentation – Chair: Rik De Vreese (European Forest Institute)

Room: HG G30.006

14.30 Coffee and tea break – networking

- 15.00 Study visit to “Microforest”
- 18.00 Gala dinner at Muraltengut (Seestrasse 203, 8002 Zurich)

DAY 3 | Friday 6th June 2025

8.00 Registration at HG E 30.0065

Conference Room: HG G 3

8.30 Parallel Session

Session 1 cont - Urban Forests for Resilient Cities

Chair: Estelle Noyer (Bern University of Applied Sciences)
Room: HG G 26.1

René van der

Velde “Cool Tree Architecture; a tree architecture typology to temper urban microclimates”

Karlién Moeys

“Cooling potential of large solitary trees: insights for urban green management”

Sophie Arzberger

“Health co-benefits of differently sized and structured public parks in Munich, Germany, as nature-based solutions for climate adaptation”

Jenny Lindern

“The potential of using small scale greenery to improve urban

Session 2 cont - Urban Forests for Healthy Cities

Chair: Reto Mohr (Grün Stadt Zürich)
Room: HG G 26.3

Zora van der Bie

“Forest Exposure Lowers Physiological Stress Markers: Exploring the Role of Forest Type and Environmental Factors”

Johanna Trummer

“Balancing Functionality and Well-Being in Urban Forest Planning”

Vincenzo Giannico

“Urban Greenness, Environmental Indicators, and Major Depressive Disorder Severity: Insights from the FREEDOM Study”

Somidh Saha

“Tree Species Diversity in Urban and Peri-urban Forests Significantly Improved Human Wellbeing in Karlsruhe,

Session 3 cont - Urban Forests for Inclusive Cities

Chair: Clémence Dirac (Federal Office for the Environment FOEN)
Room: HG G 26.5

Eleanor Smith

“UK urban forests and the 3-30-300 rule”

Anna Kajosaari

“Differences in perceived health benefits and travel distances to green space across population groups: Insights from a Public Participation GIS study”

Thomas Mattijssen

“From the inactive to the multi-tasker: insights from a large Dutch survey into individual and collective efforts in green volunteering”

Session 4 cont - Urban Forests for Sustainable Urban Planning

Chair: Stefan Stevanovic (Zurich University of Applied Sciences)
Room: HG F 33.5

Paul Haverkamp

“The potential of biodiversity effects of native and non-native species in urban ecosystems under climate warming”

Nicola Menon

“Urban and peri-urban monumental trees as biodiversity hubs: an international study across Grenoble (France), Helsinki -Espoo (Finland), and the Veneto region (Italy)”

Silviya Krajter Ostoić

“Professionals' perceptions of and attitudes towards public participation in planning and management of

resilience and attractiveness”

Michelle Leishman
“Building the resilience of the urban forest: the Australian story”

southwest Germany”

Hamza Briki Kotbani “BRERA - Wellbeing, Restoration, Resilience, and Adaptation”

Saeed Hassabelrasoul
“The Effects of Visits and Types of Activities in Forests close to urban areas on the Subjective Well-being of Visitors during and after the COVID-19 Pandemic”

Giovanni Trentanovi
“Multifaceted green areas and forests in changing cities: insights for a socio-ecological evaluation improvement”

Barbara Darr
“CommuniTree - Tea under trees: promoting urban green spaces through community engagement”

Edyta Laszkiewicz
“Would you walk here? Urban wildscapes as visual settings for utility and recreational walks”

urban trees, forests and green space”

Florim Sabani
“Initiative -Grünes Gallustal-St.Gallen”

Laura Helmin
“Bridging Technology and Citizen Engagement in Urban Forestry”

Alyssa Smolensky
“A Spatially Explicit Approach for Optimizing Urban Afforestation to Achieve Project Goals”

10.00 Coffee and tea break – networking

Room: HG E 4

10.30 Keynotes for conference theme 3 “Creating the future” – Chair: Jerylee Wilkes-Allemann (Bern University of Applied Sciences and ArboCityNet)

Room: HG G 3

Keynote 8 “From regional support to local implementation: tailoring tree policies for municipal needs” - Ward De Witte (PXL BIO-Research, PXL University of Applied Sciences and Arts)

Keynote 9 “Building Tomorrow’s Urban Landscapes: The Promise of Urban Forestry” - Simone Borelli (retired from Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations)

Keynote 10 “Resilient Tree Populations in Urban Landscapes: Insights from the City of Malmö” - Patrick Bellan (City of Malmö)

12.00 Closing session, Chair: **Andrea Gion Saluz** (Grün Stadt Zürich)

Room HG G 26.5

EFUF 2025 Summary of findings from Eugènia Vidal Casanovas (Area Metropolitana de Barcelona)

European Young Urban Forester of the Year Award 2025 from Clive Davies (EFUF & M2D Consulting)

EFUF 2026 presentation and invitation from Patrick Bellan (City of Malmö)

12.30 Ápero Riche

Room: HG E 4

13.30 Study visit to “Stadtspark”

17.00 Tropical dinner at Stadtgärtnerei (Sackzelg 27, 8047 Zurich)

DAY 4 | Saturday 7th June 2025

09.00 Half-day post conference field trip at “Recreational forest in Wallisellen” organised by Andreas Guggisberg and team (Canton of Zurich)

15.00 Departure (nearby Zurich airport)

EFUF 2025

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FRONT PAGE: KEYNOTES FOR CONFERENCE THEME 1: “RESILIENT AND HEALTHY ENVIRONMENTS: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES BETWEEN URBAN FORESTRY AND CLOSE-TO-NATURE FORESTRY”

Chair: Clive Davies (MD2 Consulting and Chairman of EFUF 2024/2025 Board)

KEYNOTE TALKS

EU scale, long term effects of integrated and adaptive forest management on Europe's forests and its forest industry

Gert-Jan Nabuurs, Wageningen University and Research (Netherlands)

Corresponding author: Gert-Jan Nabuurs, gert-jan.nabuurs@wur.nl

Abstract

The SUPERB H2020 project lays the foundation for large scale forest restoration in Europe. The pressure on forest and the needs for restoration are very different across Europe. SUPERB addresses this with 12 demo areas where restoration, monitoring, assessment and long term maintenance of practices come together in especially intense social and stakeholder processes. This talk will give an overview of achievements so far and lessons learned. Within Wageningen we also scale the processes to large areas with the European forest resource model EFISCEN-space.

17 countries covering 143 million ha of forest are represented by 308,186 NFI plots. Different scenarios were explored, assessing the impact that climate-change, disturbances (windstorms, wildfires) and adaptive forest management alternatives. The outcome of this exercise was coupled with the sawmill component of the industry module of EFISCEN-Space to assess how different scenarios will affect the sawmill value-chain. We found that forest disturbances and climate change will heavily impact European forests with a loss of growing stock of ~1.4 billion m³ throughout the century. Changing forest management by increasing species and structural diversity increases forest resilience in regions with high shares of homogeneous forests, while it is not so effective in regions where those diversities are already relatively high. Restoration can be very subtle by e.g. gradually changing to continuous cover forestry or rather dramatic in bark beetle calamity areas, up to strict set aside and old growth-ifying

The resilience of the wood value-chain increased in regions where structurally homogeneous and species poor forests were converted to mixed, structurally heterogeneous stands throughout the century, as testified by a reduced level of salvage felling and increased forest supply. However restoration can be costly and may mean that a forest resource acts as a carbon source for decades.

Biography

Gert-Jan Nabuurs is professor European forest resources at Wageningen University and Research. His expertise is European scale forest resource analyses, carbon sequestration under climate change. He is IPCC Coordinating lead Author in the Sixth Assessment Report for Agriculture and Forestry.

To re-wild or not - is this the question?

Harald Bugmann, ETH Zürich (Switzerland)

Corresponding author: Harald Bugmann, harald.bugmann@env.ethz.ch

Abstract

Rewilding of ecosystems has become a prominent concept with multiple ramifications, involving the restoration of waterways and wetlands, enhancing trophic chains by top predators, and also letting forests develop in the absence of human interventions. Yet, in the latter context the implications for long-term carbon storage and biodiversity are controversial, particularly when confronted with the alternative of the cascade use of wood products for material substitution in the building sector and bioenergy production at the end of the wood life cycle.

In Europe, forest rewilding began multiple decades ago in forest reserves, albeit often at small spatial scales. Based on the scientific network of Swiss forest reserves, I will evaluate their past and future development based on a

recent simulation modeling study, showing that in some cases drastic changes and biomass losses are likely to occur, making rewilding a debatable option at least from the carbon point of view.

As an alternative, we are exploring multiple scenarios of forest management at the regional scale to study the maximum wood production along with the biodiversity implications, showing that depending on the biogeographic setting widely different production potentials are likely to unfold in the future, thus sometimes making climate-smart forestry a better alternative compared to rewilding.

Lastly, I will explore the urban-forest interface in terms of the implications that urban forestry can have for surrounding forests, suggesting that extra care needs to be taken so as not to jeopardize future forest development by measures that are adapted to the urban context, yet not to close-to-nature forestry.

Biography

Harald Bugmann is Professor of Forest Ecology at ETH Zurich. The research of his group focuses on the impacts of global climate change on forest dynamics over decades to centuries, from tree phenology across tree growth and stand dynamics to landscape development under varying disturbance regimes. A combination of observations, partly from long-term datasets such as forest reserves, experiments and dynamic modeling are used to shed light on the patterns and processes that are shaping forest dynamics. A lot of this research is focusing on mountain forests. Providing decision support to forest practice is an important element of these activities.

Professional Credentials for Those Working in our Urban Forests

Caitlyn Pollihan, International Society of Arboriculture (United States of America)

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Abstract

ISA has recently undergone a detailed review of our ISA Certified Arborist Municipal Specialist certification. This review has culminated in a re-release of this certification as the ISA Certified Urban Forest Professional. That review included current research on the practice of urban forestry from around the world and feedback from professionals, current practitioners as well as future practitioners. ISA's volunteers that worked on this project represented urban foresters and arborists from several countries. This presentation will include data points gained during this

review about the professionals in this sector. ISA has now completed an update to the municipal specialist certification including a new name as well as new eligibility and maintenance requirements and domains. Global trends and approaches that are important for practitioners to be aware of, including 3-30-30, tree equity, and the application of nature-based solutions, are included in the knowledge base necessary for candidates. This updated exam has utility across geographic boundaries and ISA will be working with our credentialing partners in Europe and beyond to inform practitioners about these changes.

As our cities and towns continue to increase in population, our urban forests will increase in importance. Ensuring we have professionals to care for that resource is a priority and why ISA continues to invest in its programs.

Biography

Caitlyn Pollihan is the CEO and Executive Director of the International Society of Arboriculture (ISA), a role she has held since 2017 (CEO added in 2020). She has led ISA's relocation, modernization, and global outreach. Previously, she held executive roles with the Council of Western State Foresters and the Western Forestry Leadership Coalition, focusing on strategic development and public policy. Caitlyn also worked in government affairs for the Home Builders Association of St. Louis. She holds degrees in journalism and organizational communication, a nonprofit management certificate, and the Certified Association Executive (CAE) credential.

Effects of urban greenspaces on public health: serial mediation model of objective and subjective measures

Wendy Y. Chen, University of Hong Kong (China)

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Abstract

It is widely acknowledged that sufficient provision of urban greenspaces can facilitate public exposure to nature and recreational use, thereby improving public health. While both objective and subjective measures have been adopted to associate urban greenspaces with public health, little attention has been paid to the nuanced serial mediation effects of objective matrices of greenspaces on residents' subjective perception, use behaviors, and health. Using Hong Kong as a case study, this study constructed potential pathways to link objective measures of greenspace provision, subjective matrices, use behaviors, and self-rated health status, directly or indirectly via serial mediation model. Empirical results show that subjective measures of greenspaces play

significant mediating roles in associating objective greenspace provision with residents' health. This study sheds additional light on the effects of urban greenspaces on public health based on individual-level analysis in a high-density urban context. Along with enhancing greenspace provision, improving residents' satisfaction with greenspaces in their residential neighborhoods holds the promise to promote their physical interaction with and exposure to urban nature, and improve public health effectively.

Biography

Dr. Wendy Y. Chen is a professor of Department of Geography at the University of Hong Kong. She serves as the Editor-in-Chief for *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, a top international journal in the field of urban forestry and urban greening design/management. She also serves as an advisory panel member for NGOs and governmental authorities, and a review panel member for national/international research grants.

She works in the interdisciplinary field of physical and human geography, focusing on key gaps in evaluating and modelling urban green-blue spaces that are reserved, modified, and deployed in urban and peri-urban areas for their multiple benefits as well as urban livability and sustainability. Her research helps to integrate socioeconomic dimensions to enrich urban forestry scholarship, and rethink theories pertaining to the demand and supply of urban nature in the context of extensive urbanization in developing countries and re-urbanization in developed world.

FRONT PAGE: KEYNOTES FOR CONFERENCE THEME 2: CREATING HEALTHY, RESILIENT, SAFE AND EQUITABLE URBAN ENVIRONMENTS: THE POTENTIAL OF URBAN FORESTS AND PARTICIPATION”

Chair: **Cecil Konijnendijk** (Nature Based Solutions Institute and member of 2024/2025 EFUF Board)

Radical Community Engagement: A practical approach to intersectional environmental justice in urban forestry

Lotte Dijkstra, Newcastle University (United Kingdom)

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Abstract

Ensuring urban forests are accessible to all is one of the key challenges for urban forestry. Community and stakeholder engagement are perhaps the most vital processes in ensuring that urban forests and their planning, design, and management are inclusive and equitably accessible. After all, invested communities are the best advocates for and motivated caretakers of healthy, inclusive and resilient urban forests. But how can urban foresters get communities and stakeholders invested? What are the methods and tools we have at our disposal?

Over the past three years, I have explored how to foster intersectional environmental belonging in the urban forest. My PhD research *Urban Forest Stories* at Newcastle University (UK) has produced a participatory practice for radical community and stakeholder engagement. The practice is deeply rooted in the EFUF community, with parts of the methodology developed at EFUF2023 in Kraków, Poland. With this presentation, I share the key outcomes of my PhD research and offer practical applications.

I propose to define intersectional environmental access as the equitable distribution of benefits and burdens of urban forests, of procedural access through meaningful engagement in decision-making, and through the recognition of lived experiences. Community and stakeholder engagement is key to achieving this, especially procedural and recognitional access. Such community engagement needs to be radical: connected to the place, accessible to all, including historically marginalised voices, and allowing communities to foster a sense of ownership and attachment to the urban forest we are inviting them to. When we work with place, time and the more-than-human in our practices and remember to include listening, languages and lived experiences in our approach to engagement, we can make urban forests and their planning, design and management more accessible for all.

Biography

Lotte Dijkstra is a landscape architect, researcher, storyteller and artist. She explores intersectional environmentalism, radical community engagement and place-based creative methods in urban forests through her research and teaching at Newcastle University and through her company Studio PLACES. She previously contributed to research on tree architecture and the cooling effect of urban forests at Delft University of Technology and co-edited the Dutch book *Planted avenues*. On the inseparable relationship between trees and roads. She is currently completing her PhD on fostering belonging in the urban forest and preparing for exhibition at the Farrell Centre for the Built Environment in Newcastle upon Tyne, England, open to the public from October 2025 to March 2026.

Green Inequality and the Critical Role of Urban Forests in Advancing Social Integration in African Cities

Ayanda Roji, Johannesburg City Parks and Zoo & Centre on African Public Spaces (CAPS) (South-Africa)

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Abstract

Urban forests play a pivotal role in shaping inclusive, liveable, and resilient cities. Yet across many African cities, a deep spatial inequality persists in access to green infrastructure—most visibly in historically marginalised areas such as townships and informal settlements. These communities often lack even the most basic green amenities, contributing to a cycle of environmental and social exclusion that mirrors broader patterns of inequality.

This presentation will explore the concept of "green inequality" in the African urban context, using Johannesburg as a case study. It will highlight how limited tree canopy cover and poorly distributed green spaces exacerbate social divides, restrict recreational and health benefits, and reinforce historical spatial injustices. At the same time, the talk will present emerging urban forestry strategies in a number of African cities that seek to reverse these patterns—particularly through community-led greening initiatives, policy innovation, and integrated planning.

By showcasing both challenges and successes, the presentation aims to foster cross-continental dialogue on how urban forests can become tools for social integration, not only in African cities but globally. The session will also reflect on the opportunities for collaboration between African and European urban forestry networks in addressing shared urban sustainability goals.

Biography

Ayanda Roji is a practitioner at the Johannesburg City Council and Coordinator of the Centre on African Public Spaces (CAPS). She leads projects and partnerships that promote inclusive, just, and humane public spaces in African cities. In March 2025, she convened the 2nd African Forum on Urban Forests, bringing together experts, policymakers, and communities to explore the role of urban forests in city resilience. Through CAPS, Ayanda connects diverse stakeholders to advance green, integrated urban spaces. With a background in social sciences and experience in urban development and local governance, she is committed to amplifying African perspectives in shaping the continent's urban future.

Gender, Fear and Danger in Dense and Open Urban Forests

Anna Bornioli, Barcelona Institute for Global Health (Spain)

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Abstract

Perceived safety is a crucial aspect of environmental experiences in natural environments. While it is well established that dense vegetation and danger threats can hinder safety perceptions of natural environments, relatively little research has examined the role of gender in environmental experiences of nature. This study aims to clarify the role of gender in perceptions of danger, fear and preferences in natural environments and how this may interact with density of vegetation and the presence of different dangers.

The methodology is based on three experiments conducted with adults living in the Southeast of England. In Studies 1 (n=269) and 23 (n=414) participants were shown a slide show of woodlands with varying levels of density, with Study 2 being a replication of Study 1. In Study 3, 300 participants watched videos of woodlands under five different social and physical danger scenarios, and we assessed the impact of density and different dangers on perceptions of fear, risk and preferences.

All studies confirmed that women were more likely to feel at risk in natural environments than men, and more likely to express fear and concerns about dangers, especially social dangers. In Study 3, we found that women felt more fearful in all environments, especially environments with social danger threat.

Overall, the results indicate that women's experiences of nature can be affected by safety concerns to a larger extent than among men, and that these concerns are related to the density of vegetation and the presence of dangers – especially social. Tackling such potential barriers, notably safety concerns, is crucial to ensure greenspace benefits for every sociodemographic group.

Biography

Dr Anna Bornioli is a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellow at the Barcelona Institute for Global Health (ISGlobal, Spain), and a Visiting Researcher with the Environmental Psychology Research Group at the University of Surrey (United Kingdom). Her research explores nature experiences of specific gender groups, and examines how gendered safety perceptions, stereotypes, and social roles influence the way people use and perceive these spaces. Her PhD (University of the West of England, 2018) examined how city environments affect walking experiences, with a particular focus on urban parks and green historic environments.

FRONT PAGE: KEYNOTES FOR CONFERENCE THEME 3: “CREATING THE FUTURE”

Chair: **Jerylee Wilkes-Allemann** (Bern University of Applied Sciences, School of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences HAFL, ArboCityNet and member of 2024/2025 EFUF Board)

From regional support to local implementation: tailoring tree policies for municipal needs

Ward De Witte, PXL BIO-Research, PXL University of Applied Sciences and Arts (Belgium)

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Abstract

For the project ‘Climate Trees in Limburg’ in the Province of Limburg (242.231 ha, 904.000 inhabitants) in Belgium, we supported 41 of the 42 municipalities in developing data-driven tree policies and enhancing municipal staff’s knowledge and skills. The goal was to apply the latest scientific insights, such as the 3-30-300 rule, to create climate-adaptive environments where trees play a key role.

Our approach nearly doubled the number of locally approved ‘tree vision plans’ (from 11 to 19) and ‘tree policy plans’ (from 9 to 17). These policies aim to protect and increase tree

quantity and quality by setting measurable goals and providing hands-on tools. After one year, urban and peri-urban trees became a key topic in local administrations and politics.

The project’s success led to its extension by the provincial government. Updated policy documents now promote better protection of existing urban trees in development projects and ensure newly planted trees receive adequate above- and below-ground space—crucial for healthy, climate-resilient environments.

The extension focuses on practical challenges, especially urban tree management and risk mitigation. Limited experience in tree management underscores the need for guidance on plans and best practices, which will be developed with professional arborists.

Public acceptance of trees remains a challenge, as issues like fallen leaves or obstructed views persist. Public engagement is critical to building support for urban greenery and ensuring these efforts succeed.

This 1.5-year case highlights the importance of intensive support for local governments in urban forestry management and policy planning. Higher-level government support is essential for success. In this contribution, we share key lessons to inspire other regions to adopt a similar pathway.

Biography

I am a research assistant at PXL BIO-Research, part of PXL University of Applied Sciences and Arts, where I’ve been working since 2021. With a background in greenery management, I support practice-oriented research and services for governments and companies. My work includes creating urban forestry plans and advising municipalities across Limburg. In 2023, I had the privilege of supporting the entire province in strengthening urban forestry policy and practice—an experience that deepened my passion for trees and sustainable urban environments. In addition to my research role, I am also self-employed as an executive arborist.

Building Tomorrow's Urban Landscapes: The Promise of Urban Forestry

Simone Borelli, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (Italy)

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Abstract

Almost 10 years have passed since the publication of the FAO Guidelines on Urban and Peri-urban Forestry. Over the past decade, urban forestry has emerged as a cornerstone of sustainable, resilient, and inclusive city development. Once seen largely as aesthetic or recreational, urban trees are now recognized as critical green infrastructure. This presentation traces the transformation of the urban forestry sector between 2015 and 2025—driven by climate urgency, public health needs, technological advances, and social equity movements—and outlines projected developments through 2035. Key drivers of recent progress include international frameworks such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals,

the Paris Agreement, the Convention on Biological Diversity, and the UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration. Nature-based thinking has elevated the strategic value of urban forests in addressing urban heat, biodiversity loss, water regulation, and psychological well-being. Technological tools like GIS, LiDAR, and i-Tree have facilitated better data-driven urban forest management, while initiatives like Tree Cities of the World and FAO's Green Cities have helped standardize global best practices. Looking ahead, urban forestry will be increasingly shaped by smart city integration, predictive analytics, and regenerative design. Urban forests are expected to play a growing role in carbon accounting, public health policy, and climate finance. In the Global South, urban forestry will be a vital tool in managing rapid urbanization, heat stress, and social inequity, especially when paired with food-producing green spaces. This presentation highlights how urban forestry can simultaneously advance biodiversity, climate mitigation, and social justice when supported by strong policy, community engagement, and international collaboration. As cities confront 21st-century challenges, urban forests offer a tangible, scalable, and equitable solution to building greener, healthier urban futures.

Biography

Simone Borelli is a forestry expert with over 25 years of experience at the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). He led FAO's Urban Forestry Programme, providing technical support to global field projects, advising member countries on policy, and developing key publications. He played a central role in launching the World Forum on Urban Forests and the Tree Cities of the World initiative. Simone is a co-author of the FAO Guidelines on Urban and Peri-urban Forestry and the book *Urban Forestry: A Global Perspective*. His work spans community forestry, watershed restoration, and nature-based solutions for cities. He has also collaborated with WWF, Bioversity International, and various public and private institutions. He holds degrees from the University of Tuscia, the University of Arizona, and the University of London. Now retired, he continues his passion for trees at home in Lugnano in Teverina, tending to his olive grove and orchard.

Resilient Tree Populations in Urban Landscapes: Insights from the City of Malmö

Patrick Bellan, City of Malmö (Sweden)

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Abstract

Malmö, Sweden's third-largest city, has been gradually reshaping its approach to urban development by incorporating more sustainable and ecologically informed practices. A key part of this work involves improving the city's urban tree canopy to support biodiversity, address climate challenges, and enhance the quality of life for residents.

Historically, the city's tree population was heavily reliant on monocultures, which made the urban forest vulnerable to pests and disease. The impact of Dutch Elm Disease in the 1980s, which resulted in the loss of around 25% of Malmö's street trees, prompted a reassessment of these practices. Since then, Malmö has adopted strategies such as the 10-20-30 rule to encourage species diversity and reduce future risks.

Tree inventories now play a central role in planning, allowing the city to better understand species distribution and identify areas with low canopy cover. This data supports more site-appropriate planting, selecting species suited to conditions such as high temperatures and drought.

A cross-departmental Tree Group, formed in 2015, works to coordinate urban forestry efforts across city departments. Its work includes developing technical guidelines, promoting knowledge-sharing, and integrating tree planning into broader urban development processes.

In 2022, Malmö adopted the 3-30-300 principle to guide its greening goals, though the current citywide canopy cover remains at about 15%. Reaching this target presents challenges, particularly in dense areas, but the city continues to refine its strategies through tools such as canopy growth modeling and heat mapping. Malmö's experience highlights practical ways that cities can work toward a more resilient and greener urban environment. One example of this work is the "Grönare Möllan" project, which goal was to raise the canopy cover in a densely built neighborhood with minimal greenery, using planting techniques that also help manage stormwater.

Biography

Patrick Bellan is a tree specialist with the City of Malmö, focusing on both strategic urban forestry and site-specific species selection. Formerly a lecturer at the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, he has expertise in plant materials and vegetation construction. Patrick also runs a consultancy, conducts tree inventories, and leads training courses. He is president of the Swedish Tree Association, a TRAQ-certified arborist, and an active contributor to Nordic arboricultural initiatives and publications. His work is driven by a deep passion for trees and their ecological value.

Workshops

Informed Decisions, Effective Action: Credible Outcome Metrics for Urban Forestry

Daniel Griswold, United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (Switzerland)

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Abstract

Urban trees and forests can deliver many ecosystem services and benefits to society, delivering healthy, cool and resilient cities. This can help to deliver on local, national and global goals including the SDGs, climate action and the Global Biodiversity Framework.

As these forests are typically managed more intensively than forests outside cities, they can also be important repositories of genetic diversity and serve as a laboratory to study the impacts of climate change on tree species and forest structures.

This has driven attention and efforts to increase urban forests and biodiversity in cities. The question is: are these efforts effective? How can we credibly say that we have enhanced biodiversity, contributed to sustainable development objectives and/or effectively advanced climate action?

By creating a consistent framework, we can help policymakers and stakeholders make informed decisions and invest in sustainable urban greening initiatives. This will also increase the credibility of claims made about the positive impacts of urban forestry.

In this context, this session will review frameworks that look to support public and private stakeholders to answer these questions by assessing outcomes of urban forestry for biodiversity, climate and society. It will provide space to discuss whether standard metrics may facilitate action by improving data quality and availability.

A scene-setting presentation will inform discussion, presenting the findings of a study reviewing existing framework for assessing urban nature outcomes, with ideas on ways forward to support credible outcome metrics for informed decisions and effective public and private action.

Launch SPOOL journal Special Issue ‘Urban Forest-scapes’

René van der Velde, Delft University of Technology (Netherlands)

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Abstract

This event showcases work from the recently-released special issue of the journal SPOOL, on the topic of Urban Forestscapes (<https://spool.ac/index.php/spool/issue/view/28>). Research papers and visual essays in this volume elaborate a designerly perspective on urban forestry, engaging with aspects such as Urban Forestscapes in the Metropolitan Mosaic, Experience and Experimentation, Living Labs, Large-scale Urban Projects, Political Narratives and Historical Evidence. Contributions are from Scandinavia, the Netherlands, Belgium, Switzerland, Italy and Georgia. The event is an official launch and includes sharing and discussing key outcomes with authors and participants.

Movie about the “Grünes Gallustal” initiative

Florim Sabani, Verein Grünes Gallustal (Switzerland)

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Abstract

Grünes Gallustal (gruenesgallustal.ch) serves as a pioneering framework to advance sustainability and enhance the quality of life in the city of St. Gallen, Switzerland. Developed through a bottom-up approach led by civil society, this initiative presents 14 carefully designed planning measures aimed at climate adaptation, biodiversity enhancement, and urban improvement. The measures range in complexity—from small-scale interventions such as tree planting and the reversal of soil sealing, to larger urban projects, including watercourse restoration and highway capping. Each measure is supported by clear, measurable sub-objectives.

The full planning concept behind Grünes Gallustal is documented in a 1,500-page blueprint, the result of a three-year interdisciplinary collaboration involving 20 experts. It integrates scientific analysis, climate mapping, and before-and-after visualisations to provide decision-makers with a clear roadmap for action. The blueprint has received broad support from the city administration and political leaders, who now view Grünes Gallustal as an informal green master plan. Initial pilot projects in the city’s east, such as the *Areal Bach* and the “Edible Park” in Stephanshorn, have already been successfully implemented, demonstrating the feasibility and positive impact of the proposed strategies.

To clearly convey the scope and potential of the project, a 30-minute documentary film was produced in collaboration with Leica Geosystems, part of Hexagon. The film translates complex planning data into engaging visual narratives. Through expert commentary and grounded technical insight, it illustrates how targeted greening efforts can reshape urban spaces and promote climate resilience—not only in St. Gallen but in cities around the world.

At the core of the film are digital simulations derived from over 100 billion data points captured using Leica’s CityMapper-2 hybrid airborne sensor. This technology enabled the creation of a highly accurate digital twin of the city of St. Gallen, which served as a basis for immersive fly-throughs and visual transformations that show how targeted greening measures can reshape urban areas into climate-resilient, livable environments. The visualisations, both 2D and 3D, make abstract planning concepts tangible and engaging—bridging the gap between scientific insight, political decision-making, and public understanding.

Inspired by forward-thinking urban models from cities like Medellín, Vienna, and London, Grünes Gallustal promotes an integrated and scalable approach to sustainable urban development. With its emphasis on low-barrier citizen participation, cross-sector collaboration, and visual accessibility, it stands as Switzerland’s first comprehensive green urban planning concept—providing a replicable model for other cities navigating the challenges of climate change and urbanisation.

The film serves as both a communication tool and a catalyst—bringing the project’s core ideas to life in a format that resonates across disciplines. Whether viewed by policymakers, planners, or the public, it fosters a shared understanding of what a greener, more livable urban future can look like.

www.gruenesgallustal.ch/film

About

The Grünes Gallustal association works to make St.Gallen greener and to further enhance its quality of life. It encourages both public and private stakeholders to help bring nature back into the city and to address the impacts of climate change. The association contributes ideas to participatory processes and provides advice to the city, the canton, and private individuals. www.gruenesgallustal.ch

Picture 1: Visualisation of the daylighting of the “Steinach” stream and its greening in the old town of St.Gallen

Picture 2: still image from the film “Grünes Gallustal”, modeled simulation using Leica’s CityMapper-2 hybrid airborne sensor.

FRONT PAGE FOR PARALLEL SESSION 1:
URBAN FORESTS FOR RESILIENT CITIES

Greening the urban edge towards climate neutrality and resilience. The metropolitan area of Barcelona participation in the Horizon Commit2Green project.

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Abstract

This paper discusses the strategic contribution of managing and planning urban forest edges to resilience. In order to do that, it focuses on the Horizon Commit2Green [C2G] project and the pilot in the metropolitan area of Barcelona [AMB].

AMB covers an area of 636km² that encompasses 36 municipalities with 3.35 million inhabitants. Despite this high density, only 48% of the area corresponds to developed land. Forests and other blue and green open spaces occupy the other 52%. The contact and interaction between these two coexisting realities post many challenges and opportunities.

C2G supports 8 cities to move away for a project-by-project NBS intervention approach towards the development of greening and renaturing strategies towards climate neutrality and resilience that are cross-scalar and participatory, inform existing development agendas and policies, and are implemented through pilots that create tangible impact on the ground of the local communities and broader ecosystem. This paradigm shift is founded on the operationalization of Ecosystem Services [ES] in city decision-making at the district and city scale.

The pilot in the AMB is located at the urban edge between a low-income residential and industrial district and a forest area with several minor streams. The pilot aims at identifying and testing innovative NBS for managing the edge through co-design processes with the local communities and a nearby school. The identified challenges are: (1) lack of public space, (2) intense heat stress, (3) a negative landscape image of abandonment, with continuously and uncontrolled dumps and improper uses, and (4) the alteration of hydrological fluxes, with the development of extensive grey drainage infrastructure with limited infiltration, increased runoff and depleted water tables results. The learnings of managing this fringe area will be used as a case study for replication in similar sites, improving policy and testing new urban planning approaches.

A tree language for Rotterdam. Guiding principles for a creative management culture

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Abstract

In 2024 the management department of the municipality Rotterdam asked Delft University of Technology researchers for a durable and future-proof decision-making method for tree maintenance in parks and plantations, based on Tree Language. Tree language is a typology of urban tree structures, which characterizes the spatial relationship between tree species, configurations and plantations (vocabulary, syntax and structure) and their specific situation. It provides a neutral framework for decision-making; the socio-cultural, economic, physical and ecological dimension provide the content. Urban tree structures derive their logic from the anchoring in the *longue durée* of their development, and from a scale continuity in which the different dimensions play out. Therefore, the method starts from understanding the existing mosaic of plantations, tree types and configurations in relation to each other as the basis for future transformations. To make the tree language operational for management we studied three cases of different sizes and complexity: Buizenpark is small and part of a neighbourhood plantation structure, Valkeniersweide is a clearly defined urban park and Drechterweide is a large forest plantation. We used the case studies to define different steps: determine 1) type of plantation; 2) tree types; 3) configurations; 4) groups of configurations; 5) Proposal for strengthening existing groups and configurations, with a basic and maximum version as a tool for discussion with different actors. This provides a solid starting point for the next two steps, to be conducted in collaboration with the municipal departments: 6) Compare to ongoing plans; 7) Differentiate in time. This asks for two transitions in management paradigms: 1) Spatial dimension as basis; 2) Configuration instead of forest plantation or individual tree as management unit. Merging a landscape architectural and a maintenance perspective, we might speculatively call this method a 'creative management strategy'.

Aesculus - quo vadis?

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Abstract

Aesculus hippocastanum, the horse chestnut, has characterized many cities in Central Europe for centuries. Hardly any other tree is so well suited to illustrate the effects of stress factors and negative site and environmental influences.

Although this tree species is generally considered to be extremely robust, it is under increasing pressure from a variety of stress factors. The main factors include the chestnut leaf miner, plant pathogenes like *Pseudomonas syringae*, soil sealing, drought stress and heat radiation. For many inner-city and historic green spaces planted with horse chestnut trees however, there are no proven strategies to preserve the tree population in the long term.

The situation is even more critical due to increasing loss of habitat in the natural distribution areas of the horse chestnut in the south-eastern Balkans (Greece, Albania and North Macedonia). Because of the endangerment of the populations, ex-situ conservation culture is being considered.

Using the example of the Hirschengraben in Bern, a late 19th century promenade with 25 horse chestnut trees, the challenges and possible solutions for the future of the horse chestnut in Europe will be presented. We would like to initiate a discussion about how to take care of *Aesculus hippocastanum* within the urban forest in order to preserve this culturally and historically valuable tree species.

Unravelling Adaptive Resilience, Tolerance Mechanisms, and Mitigation Potential of Roadside Tree Species to Vehicular Emissions across Urban Habitats

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Abstract

Urban roadside trees (URT) are crucial in mitigating air pollution and enhancing city ecosystem services. However, vehicular emissions and human activities in urban areas poses significant physiological, and biochemical challenges to their resilience. This study elucidates the adaptive resilience and tolerance mechanisms of URTs subjected to vehicular emissions across various urban habitats. A plant functional trait-based approach was employed to assess seasonal modulations in physiological responses, biochemical adaptations, and air pollution tolerance of five roadside tree species in habitats dominated by industrial, vehicular, and societal activities, as well as control sites. We evaluated adaptive resilience by assessing functional traits such as stomatal conductance, transpiration, water use efficiency, nitrogen use efficiency, leaf thickness, proline accumulation, and total sugars. Air pollution tolerance was determined using the air pollution tolerance index (APTI), calculated based on antioxidant levels, chlorophyll content, relative water content, and leaf pH. The mitigation efficiency of tree species was evaluated by examining carbon assimilation, dust load capacity, and cooling effects of trees across studied habitats. All functional traits varied significantly across species and environmental conditions. The findings revealed that tree species with higher adaptive resilience and air pollution tolerance exhibited greater mitigation efficiency toward urban climate conditions and vehicular emissions. Furthermore, this study provides essential scientific insights into tree species adaptive resilience, tolerance, and mitigation efficiency in response to vehicular pollution. This approach may assist urban planners and policymakers in selecting appropriate species for green belts and urban green spaces to adapt to and mitigate urban climate challenges and vehicular emissions.

Keywords: Vehicular emissions, Plant functional traits, Physiology and biochemistry

Bigger Roots, Stronger Cities: Rethinking Tree Watering for Climate Resilience

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Abstract

I propose presenting a slightly modified version of the session from the ISA Annual Conference 2024 in Atlanta. Lynsey Nielson and I discussed the impact of watering established trees. A major issue is shallow rooting and limited root systems due to irrigation, leading to instability and reduced drought resilience. Newly planted trees under automatic irrigation face similar problems. Yet, few seriously examine how irrigation methods impact tree stability and long-term health.

As drought spreads, those in newly affected areas look to regions with longer experience for guidance. If these regions have adopted poor watering practices, mistakes may be repeated, leading to further tree loss. It's time to open this discussion and take a proactive approach.

Research confirms that retaining and improving the health of established trees provides significantly more ecosystem services than planting new ones. Yet, with increasing drought, heat waves, and irregular precipitation, large trees are suffering. Water is becoming an ever-scarcer resource, and irrigation practices often fail to support tree health while wasting water. In many cases, irrigation itself puts trees at risk. How can arborists balance resource conservation with effective care for these trees?

In 2020, Salt Lake City lost thousands of trees in a single windstorm. Arborists identified poor watering practices, particularly shallow irrigation, as a key factor in tree failure. Using this example, I will explore the consequences of past water management strategies, their effects on mature trees, and solutions based on tree biology to improve resilience and conserve water.

This presentation aims to highlight a critical gap in holistic tree management, emphasizing the role of proper watering in climate change adaptation. By optimizing irrigation, we can not only sustain urban forests but also leverage trees for microclimate cooling, maximizing their ecosystem services in an era of climate emergency.

Strengthening the business case for urban forests

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Abstract

Nature-based solutions (NBS) are increasingly recognized as effective strategies for addressing urbanization challenges while enhancing environmental sustainability and community well-being. Urban forests, in particular, play a crucial role in climate adaptation and urban resilience. However, decision-making around their funding and implementation is often centralized within public authorities and government bodies, overlooking input from local communities, NGOs, and small to medium enterprises, which are key stakeholders directly impacted by green infrastructure decisions. This limited engagement, coupled with a lack of awareness of the long-term economic, environmental and social benefits of urban forests, frequently hampers the realization of their full potential and long-term viability.

To bridge this gap, the Horizon 2020 CONEXUS project has developed the step-by-step guide "Capturing the Values and Making the Business Case for Nature-Based Solutions". Designed to empower urban stakeholders, this guide provides structured methodologies and practical tools for developing robust business case for NBS; shifting the focus from a narrow economic perspective to a comprehensive valorization approach that integrates environmental, economic, social and health dimensions.

Tested in five cities across Europe and Latin America, the methodology proposed in the Guide has been adapted to diverse socio-economic and political contexts, addressing challenges related to data availability, governance structures and stakeholder engagement. Integrating urban forests into a structured business case framework could ensure that these infrastructures receive not only financial support for implementation but also sustained community participation, maximizing their impact and ensuring long-term social and financial viability.

Greening Cities, Growing Value: How PEFC Trees Outside Forests Certification Transforms Urban Forestry in the Netherlands

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Abstract

Urban forestry is vital for creating resilient, healthy, and sustainable urban environments. According to the FAO, decentralizing and empowering local communities in resource management can boost the conservation and sustainable use of Trees Outside Forests (TOF). This study examines the impact of implementing the Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) standard for TOF in urban environments, focusing on the Netherlands as a case study. PEFC TOF standards have recently been endorsed in Portugal, the UK, and India, with ongoing developments in Italy, France, Bulgaria, Indonesia, and Thailand. In each of these countries, diverse working groups adapt the PEFC benchmark requirements to local contexts, reflecting unique environmental, social, and economic conditions. Third-party certification provides independent verification of sustainable practices, enhancing credibility and fostering public trust in municipal operations. The Dutch implementation of PEFC TOF certification demonstrates its potential to create new market opportunities, particularly in sustainability-focused sectors. Italy's emphasis on Green Public Procurement compliance for contracts and ecosystem services in urban green spaces presents significant investment prospects. Key standard requirements include maintaining tree cover and diversity by adopting sustainable management practices, active stakeholder engagement, and safeguards for workers and trees during construction activities. Collectively, such elements ensure that urban forestry practices contribute to environmental sustainability, social well-being, and economic viability. This study demonstrates the significant benefits and potential of PEFC TOF certification, urging cities worldwide to embrace these standards to safeguard a greener, healthier future. By adopting PEFC TOF certification, municipalities can pioneer sustainable urban forestry, aligning with global best practices and raising the bar for others to follow.

Urban Governance Toolbox for Climate Adaptation

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Abstract

Cities and municipalities are under threat of climate-related issues such as heavy rain and heat waves. Therefore, the European Union and the German Federal Ministry of Research and Education established the SMARTilience program to support cities and municipalities in implementing resilient planning strategies. As part of the project, Drees & Sommer co-developed the "Urban Governance Toolbox" website, where municipal employees can find helpful tips and suggestions for designing implementation processes for climate protection and adaptation. In addition, Drees & Sommer was commissioned to apply and adapt this toolbox in the City of Mannheim in order to ensure optimal handling for other cities and municipalities. The presentation will reflect on the lessons-learned in the integrated strategies for the implementation of the Toolbox recommendations.

Cool Tree Architecture; a tree architecture typology to temper urban microclimates

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Abstract

As the ‘mainframe’ of green infrastructure, the urban forest is recognized as vital to the adaptation of cities to deal with urban heat extremes. But while it is common knowledge that trees contribute to cooling through shading, it remains unclear what each tree species cooling contribution is. Current indicators of potential cooling performances such as gap fraction and leaf area index overlook the more complex combination of traits of urban trees that lead to thermal amelioration. This paper elaborates on a study to develop a “Cool Tree Architecture Typology” (C-TAT), involving a structured and comprehensive overview of the physical characteristics that deliver the cooling performance of trees in urban environments. It hypothesizes by extension, that trees with a similar C-TAT profile have comparable cooling performances. The C-TAT framework builds on the foundations of tree architecture, a field of study that understands trees in terms of their physiognomy, morphology, and morphogenesis. A multi-year study was done of 69 similarly-aged young specimens of different tree species common to Cfb climate zone cities. These were installed in above-ground planter boxes in a paved courtyard area on the TU university campus in the city of Delft in the Netherlands. The results of the study show that six sub-traits together impact reflection, absorption and transmission of radiation. These include Crown Density, Wood Zoning, Foliage Porosity, Foliage Trans-luminescence and Wood Grain. Based on this order of traits an overall ranking of the trees was established, with the 69 species reduced to a total of 51 architectural types. An abbreviated type was also trialed, considering Crown Density and Foliage Trans-luminescence only as traits with the least crossover in terms of characteristics. This clustering resulted in nine architectural types.

Cooling potential of large solitary trees: insights for urban green management

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Abstract

Large solitary trees (LSTs) are keystone structures in urban and rural landscapes, serving as green islands that host a broad range of biodiversity and ecosystem functions. With their large and well-developed crowns, LSTs significantly influence local microclimatic conditions. However, LSTs are globally declining due to land-use changes, infrastructure development and age-related pests and pathogens. Their isolated nature makes them more susceptible to climatic stresses, such as droughts and heat waves, compared to forest trees. In urban areas, these effects are further exacerbated by the urban heat island effect, where buildings and concrete surfaces amplify warming. Climate change challenges the growth and vitality of LSTs, while their mitigating effects on the climate are needed now more than ever.

This study explores the cooling potential of LSTs during heat events with a particular focus on the relationship between cooling effects and the tree's morphological characteristics, such as the starting height of the crown, crown volume, and branching angle. We measured temperatures at a height of three meters along the trunks of 216 LSTs from summer 2022 to spring 2024 and compared these to temperatures around the tree extracted from the R-package microclimf. We focused on three widely spread and iconic tree species: *Quercus robur*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, and *Tilia cordata*. These trees were selected across an urban-rural gradient in nine cities throughout temperate Europe. Using a terrestrial laser scanner, we obtained leaf-off point clouds for each tree, providing a unique dataset on their morphology. We hypothesized that species selection and specific morphological characteristics, controllable by management practices, will significantly affect the cooling ability of urban trees. Our findings aim to provide valuable insights for urban planners and managers, highlighting how urban green management can optimize the cooling benefits of trees in cities.

Health co-benefits of differently sized and structured public parks in Munich, Germany, as nature-based solutions for climate adaptation

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Abstract

Public parks are a critical measure to adapt cities to climate change while providing valuable co-benefits that promote human wellbeing. To realize these potentials, we need to understand how the spatial configuration of parks is linked to their health-promoting potentials. To identify synergies and trade-offs between the health co-benefits, we applied methods from forestry, urban climatology, environmental psychology, and public health. We selected 61 plots in 36 public parks in Munich, Germany. The parks cover a gradient in size and vegetation structural complexity, ranging from sparse to forest-like. To characterize the vegetation structure, we applied mobile laser scanning, and to investigate the local cooling effects, we monitored the microclimate in the park plots and in their urban surroundings. To describe the subjective thermal comfort, activities, and mental restoration, we observed and surveyed visitors in the plots.

Parks with a complex vegetation structure provided up to 3.3 °C cooling on hot days, while parks with low complexity were partially warmer than their surroundings. While large parks generally provided greater cooling, vegetation complexity partially compensated for the size differences. Regardless of size, old parks with high trees and a large canopy cover were key to urban cooling. The mental restoration was high across all parks. Large parks were perceived as slightly more restorative, while vegetation complexity had no direct impact. Parks with moderate vegetation complexity indirectly enhanced restoration by promoting higher thermal comfort and inviting for longer visits. Activity patterns varied with size: small parks encouraged social and cultural interactions while large parks favored strolling. Overall, we conclude that small parks with moderate vegetation complexity serve as effective climate adaptation measures, offering cooling and thermal comfort on hot days while supporting activities that promote mental wellbeing year-round.

The potential of using small scale greenery to improve urban resilience and attractiveness

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Abstract

Despite the well-documented benefits of urban greenery, cities continue to struggle to meet their greening targets. Urban greening efforts often focus on trees, which require significant space both above and below ground. However, the intense competition for limited urban space presents a major challenge. To take a more realistic approach to achieving greenery goals, trees must be complemented by small-scale green solutions such as green roofs, green walls, and plant beds.

In our research, we collaborate with the city of Malmö, Sweden, to identify to identify plantable spots and practically feasible green solutions in areas that typically lack vegetation. We compare the potential for increasing greenery using trees alone versus a combination of trees and small-scale greenery. Additionally, we assess possibilities for further greening if current regulatory constraints are updated favourably. Furthermore, we conduct an in-depth evaluation of the developed greenery scenarios to quantify their impact on various ecosystem services, with a particular focus on enhancing thermal comfort, improving air quality, and shaping residents' perceptions of the urban spaces.

Our overarching goal is to identify which types of greenery are suitable in different types of environments, address relevant conflicts and synergies, and fill knowledge gaps to present a holistic analysis of the multifunctionality of each solution.

Here, we present the designed scenarios, explore the potential of small-scale greening strategies to enhance urban greenery, and present preliminary quantification of how these solutions can improve the resilience and attractiveness of our cities.

Building the resilience of the urban forest: the Australian story

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Abstract

Urban forests provide a multitude of ecosystem services for our cities and their inhabitants, from temperature reduction and stormwater management to habitat for biodiversity, and improved health and wellbeing. To ensure these services are maximised, cities require healthy and resilient urban forests. Increased temperatures and shifts in rainfall patterns as well as new pests and diseases due to climate change are putting pressure on our existing urban forest. To understand urban forest vulnerability we (1) undertook a survey of over 5000 street trees after an extreme heat event in western Sydney and assessed foliage damage across species and economic costs of replacement; and (2) assessed the diversity of urban forests at the local government level across Australia. We then developed the 'Which Plant Where' online plant selector tool, a climate-ready plant selector tool containing information for over 2500 plant species, hybrids and cultivars, designed to inform climate-ready plant selection for Australian urban environments. The tool is underpinned by species distribution models, allowing users to select climatically-suitable species for three time periods (2030, 2050, 2070), for chosen locations at postcode-level. Which Plant Where also contains information on growth characteristics and environmental tolerances to aid in plant selection, provides quantitative data on total canopy cover and planting diversity, and allows users to calculate co-benefits based on shade, carbon and biodiversity values, based on selected planting palettes. To facilitate successful and resilient urban green spaces, the tool also provides resources and best practice guides covering climate change, resilient urban landscapes, planning, monitoring and maintenance, and community engagement. We discuss planned improvements and additions, based on user experience and feedback

FRONT PAGE FOR PARALLEL SESSION 2:
URBAN FORESTS FOR HEALTHY CITIES

LiDAR-based Assessment of Urban Tree Benefits from a OneHealth perspective

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Abstract

Urban treescapes uniquely contribute to healthier and more resilient cities. By providing a wide range of ecosystem services, urban trees help combat climate change, enhance biodiversity, and improve public health. These benefits align with the One Health framework, which highlights the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health. While public initiatives, such as urban tree-planting schemes, often receive significant attention from scientists and policymakers, the substantial role of trees in private spaces, including domestic gardens, remains underexplored. While gardens cover more than one third of Western European urban areas and offer untapped potential for fostering One Health, research on their contribution, particularly across urbanization gradients, is limited. Our study addresses this gap by quantifying and comparing ecosystem services provided by garden trees, street trees, and public trees in Flanders, Belgium. Ecosystem services were analyzed across five urban sprawl typologies in 13 cities. Consistent with the One Health framework, we categorized urban tree benefits into three clusters: (1) biodiversity enhancement, (2) climate adaptation and mitigation, and (3) human well-being. Using Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) data, we segmented tree canopies and derived dendrometric characteristics, which were used in connectivity analysis and i-Tree ECO software to assess the trees' contributions to ecosystem services. Our findings reveal that garden trees contribute 5-8% of ecosystem service provision compared to street and public trees in open area, 15-28% in dispersed development, 30-47% in allotment and ribbon development, 34-47% in urban periphery and 29-42% in urban core. These results underscore their importance in urban planning and green infrastructure management and stress the need for inclusive approaches that integrate garden trees into sustainable urban development for all.

High transpiration cooling by urban trees despite extreme summer heatwaves

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Abstract

Urban trees cool their environment by transpiration (latent heat flux, LE) and shading, modifying thereby the energy budget and alleviating urban heat. The cooling effect from LE may be critically reduced during heatwaves, when trees reduce stomatal conductance (g_s) to prevent hydraulic dysfunctions. Recent advances in our understanding of stomatal behaviour under high temperatures indicate that g_s may still be maintained during extreme heat to allow canopy cooling, but implications for urban heat stress mitigation remain elusive.

We continuously recorded sap flow on eight *Platanus x acerifolia* trees in Geneva to assess LE and canopy conductance (G_{Asw}) during the summer of 2023, which was characterised by two record-breaking heatwaves. We further repeatedly assessed stomatal conductance (g_s), and leaf, canopy, and ground surface temperatures in shaded and sunlit parts around the trees. Using the ecohydrological model UT&C, we determined the total energy budget of the urban square.

We found that despite prolonged heatwaves with air temperature (T_{air}) reaching 39.1 °C, trees continued transpiring throughout the day up to 37.1 kg h⁻¹ (i.e. LE of 25.3 kW). LE was similar during heatwaves (i.e., $T_{air} > 30$ °C) as during cooler periods and accounted for approximately 34 % of the urban heating by incoming solar radiation (Q^*). In contrast, LE model predictions showed a marked decrease of urban cooling during heatwaves, thereby underestimating actual tree transpiration cooling.

Despite unprecedentedly high T_{air} during two summer heatwaves, trees maintained high transpiration, and thereby efficiently cooled the urban environment. Measured LE at T_{air} above 30 °C surpassed model estimations due to continued tree transpiration. Consequently, actual cooling effects of urban trees during heatwaves might be considerably underestimated by current model predictions. Cities with intermittent heatwaves may thus continue to rely on effective vegetation cooling by transpiration.

The perception of public green spaces in Portugal with the focus on Lisbon

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Abstract

The expansion of urban forests in many cities by implementing more green infrastructures has been reported as a way to promote health, well-being, and resilience. Urban trees contribute to the quality of urban life, with positive impact in improving air quality, reducing the ambient temperature, increasing humidity, promoting biodiversity, mitigating climate change and enhancing the landscape.

We implemented a survey of 924 random Portuguese adults in 2024 to investigate the use of public green spaces in Portugal by identifying their frequency of use and perceived benefits of green spaces. Our findings reveal that half of the respondents has a green space within a 5-minute walk from their home, with 85% indicating less than a 15-minute walk to a nearby green space. Moderating temperature and reducing air pollution emerged as the main benefits that respondents found in having more green spaces in their cities with many prioritizing urban comfort and relaxation over physical activity or social interaction. Over 95% of the respondents consider that green spaces are positive for public health and well-being. Even though, 6% of those respondents consider that trees cause more damage than benefits.

We focused on the city of Lisbon to compare the use of green spaces in a time span of 20 years. By comparing the 2024 results with those of a 2004 survey, with 1010 respondents, we concluded that there was a twofold increase in the use of green spaces mainly by active female aged 45-65 years. Physical activity and urban comfort still are the main reasons for using these spaces. Over 90% of the respondents supported the idea that a percentage of the municipal tax should be allocated to urban tree management and for planting more trees in green spaces.

These results are in line with other survey outputs from European cities, mainly after the pandemic periods, revealing that citizens are now more aware of the impact of trees and green spaces in improving health and well-being.

Effects of school indoor environments and green spaces on mental health of adolescent pupils: A crossover experiment

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Abstract

Adolescents spend many hours a day at school and are subject to intensive cognitive demands. Relaxation breaks during the school day are therefore important for school pupils in order to remain cognitively receptive and restore attention, respectively. The question arises as to which sites in the school or in the school environment are more or less suitable for providing health benefits. The study compared the restorative effects of different indoor and outdoor school environments on adolescent pupils in Vienna, Austria, during the vegetated season. 78 pupils (15-18 years) participated in a cross-over experiment measuring state of mind (Nitsch scale), cognitive performance (d2-R Test of Attention), and perceived health benefits in indoor and outdoor green environments (urban forests and parks) before and after the (main) 30-minute break. Regardless of the environment visited, pupils reported higher health benefits and better state of minds after the break - even after spending time in the classroom. In terms of state of mind and cognitive performance, the short-term measurements could not prove that green environments worked better than the indoor environments such as the classroom or break room.

Tree Performance and Cooling Benefits in Multi-layered Urban Forests

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Abstract

Urban forests are vital for climate adaptation, mitigating heat stress and enhancing thermal comfort in cities. However, among many influencing factors, their effectiveness depends on vegetation structure and composition. While trees provide cooling benefits, their functioning is influenced by complex interactions with ground surface characteristics and understory vegetation. These interactions pose a management challenge: understory vegetation may compete with trees for water and nutrients, while also influencing the local microclimate through enhanced transpiration and modified surface energy balance. This dynamic remains underexplored in urban forest planning, where selecting optimal vegetation combinations to balance thermal comfort and water use needs careful consideration.

Our research examines these relationships by studying two tree species with contrasting morphological and physiological traits—*Robinia pseudoacacia* and *Acer platanoides*—under three configurations: tree-impervious, tree-grass, and tree-shrub-grass. Through monitoring in summer in Munich (2023-2024), we employed weather stations, soil moisture sensors, sap flow measurements, and gas analyzers to assess how different vegetation combinations affect tree water use, transpirational cooling, and human thermal comfort.

Preliminary results show 20% variation in tree water use across understory configurations. *R.pseudoacacia* exhibited 27% lower transpiration in tree-shrub-grass sites compared to tree-grass-only sites, while *A.platanoides* showed no significant differences between combinations. Cooling effects, measured as Physiological Equivalent Temperature reductions, varied by up to 4.2°C, with maximum cooling in tree-shrub-grass configurations. These findings demonstrate understory vegetation's significant influence on tree performance and cooling benefits, providing urban planners with insights on optimizing urban forest structure to maximize ecosystem services and improve urban microclimates.

Green areas and mortality: a health impact assessment in the Florentine plain

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION

With ~76% of population residing in urban areas, Europe has a high urbanization rate, expected to grow further. Urban expansion challenges public health, particularly amid climate change. Green spaces mitigate these effects, benefiting physical and mental health and reducing mortality.

OBJECTIVE

This study quantifies the impact of green space exposure on avoidable deaths at the census tract level in 2021 in an urban area of Tuscany, including Florence and seven neighbouring municipalities. The analysis focuses on medium/long-term effects, comparing actual exposure with counterfactual scenarios of increased greenery.

METHOD

Exposure was assessed using the 2015 average Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) within 300m of each tract. Deaths in 2021 were estimated by redistributing municipality-level mortality data based on the tract-level demographics. Relative risks from literature adjusted for social deprivation. Mortality impacts were estimated for individuals aged over 35 years under three scenarios: (A) NDVI thresholds (0.5, 0.7, WHO-recommended), (B) +20% NDVI, and (C) +0.1 NDVI. The WHO threshold (25% green space) was converted to NDVI via a validated model. The exposure-response curve was estimated using a Bayesian replication of a recent meta-analysis. Uncertainty was accounted for via Monte Carlo simulations.

RESULTS

Estimated avoidable deaths: 335 [90% uncertainty interval: 0–785] for NDVI ≥ 0.5 ; 830 [0–1896] for NDVI ≥ 0.7 . A +0.1 NDVI and +20% NDVI increase would save 305 [0–723] and 248 [0–585] deaths, respectively. The WHO threshold (NDVI = 0.33) suggests 54 avoidable deaths [0–128]. The central, with lower NDVI, showed the highest improvement potential.

CONCLUSIONS

Despite uncertainties, the impact is substantial. Urban forestry policies can mitigate avoidable deaths, highlighting the broader risks of green space scarcity. This approach can help public administrators recognize the value of investing in urban green spaces.

Differential Immune Modulation Following Short-Term Exposure to Two Forest Types Compared to an Urban Environment

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Abstract

The prevalence of non-communicable diseases (NCDs), including immune disorders such as allergies and autoimmunity has risen since the start of industrialization and is now the leading cause of mortality worldwide. The evolutionary mismatch hypothesis argues that the rise in NCDs is a consequence of humans evolving in habitats vastly different from the highly industrialised environments we live in today.

While prior research has examined the effects of diet, antibiotics and chronic stress on immune function, the role of different environments remains understudied. Forest exposure is associated with increased natural killer (NK) cell levels, higher cytotoxic cytokine expression (granzyme and perforin) and lower levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines. However, previous studies showing these relationships have been limited in scope, focused on isolated immune markers, were constrained by small sample sizes and took a homogeneous view of nature that did not consider ecological differences between environments.

This randomized-controlled study (N=77) investigates how immune function is affected by a 3-hour exposure to one of two forest types (deciduous: Sihlwald, Zurich and coniferous: Parc Jura Vaudois, Lausanne) or an industrialised urban centre (Zurich City). Venous blood was collected pre- and post-intervention and analyzed using flow cytometry. We characterized 18 immune cell populations, with 4 cytokines assessed in a subset of 8 functionally relevant populations.

Our findings suggest that short-term exposure to different environments can modulate innate and adaptive immunity. Forest exposure was linked to reduced antigen-presenting cells, increased naïve T cells and elevated CD8+ and CD4+ effector T cells. Cytokine changes were limited. Previously reported differences in NK cells and granzyme levels were not replicated. While some effects were subtle, the overall pattern may reflect environmentally driven modulation, potentially involving circadian rhythm alignment.

Forest Exposure Lowers Physiological Stress Markers: Exploring the Role of Forest Type and Environmental Factors

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Abstract

More than half of the global population resides in urban areas. While offering numerous benefits, urbanisation is also associated with an increased prevalence of chronic stress, causing systemic health issues. A growing body of evidence suggests that spending time in forests, compared to urban environments, lowers physiological stress biomarkers. However, the effects of different forest types and underlying mechanistic interactions remain poorly understood.

We conducted a randomised controlled trial to investigate the physiological effects of a three-hour guided hike in either a deciduous forest (Sihlwald, near Zurich), a coniferous forest (Parc Jura Vaudois, near Lausanne) or an urban environment (Zürich City). A range of stress biomarkers (heart rate (HR), heart rate variability (HRV), systolic and diastolic blood pressure (SBP and DBP) and salivary cortisol) was assessed pre- and post-intervention in 161 participants. Environmental parameters (meteorological, acoustic, visual, air pollution, air chemical composition and radiation) were continuously monitored throughout each intervention.

Exposure to forest environments significantly reduced HR, HRV and DBP compared to the urban environment, while SBP and cortisol were not significantly affected. No significant physiological differences were observed between the coniferous and deciduous groups. Initial analyses indicate potential links between stress markers and environmental factors including temperature, airborne ultrafine particles and acoustic indices.

Our results build upon previous research by providing evidence that different types of forests may offer similar stress-reducing benefits while also highlighting environmental factors that might influence physiological stress. These findings underscore the sensitivity of human physiology to environmental conditions and emphasise the importance of accessible green spaces and intact natural ecosystems for public health.

Balancing Functionality and Well-Being in Urban Forest Planning

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Abstract

Urban forests are key to climate adaptation, recreation, and public health, yet their design and management often prioritize accessibility and maintenance over psychological restoration. This study examines how urban forest planning can better integrate social, ecological, and spatial data to enhance both visitor satisfaction and well-being.

Using a nationwide Public Participatory Geographic Information System (PPGIS) survey and Swiss National Forest Inventory (NFI) data, we analyze spatial patterns of urban forest use, perceived attractiveness, and mental well-being. Results reveal for example a striking disparity in Zürich: while urban forests in the metropolitan area show high satisfaction with maintenance and recreation infrastructure, they fail to provide strong well-being benefits. Visitors appreciate functional accessibility and structured management, yet these forests rank low in perceived visual attractiveness and restorative experiences.

Key findings indicate that:

- Highly structured and well-maintained forests are frequently visited but do not always foster mental restoration.
- Forests with diverse vegetation and "wild" elements tend to enhance well-being but may conflict with traditional urban forestry maintenance goals.
- Physical accessibility alone does not drive forest use-personal connection and perceived naturalness play a stronger role.

These insights highlight the need for a dual approach in urban forest planning: ensuring high functional usability while also creating spaces that support solitude, immersion, and psychological restoration. We propose strategies such as designating quiet zones, reducing visible management interventions, and enhancing forest diversity to balance recreation, biodiversity, and well-being.

Urban Greenness, Environmental Indicators, and Major Depressive Disorder Severity: Insights from the FREEDOM Study

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of urban greenness on the severity of Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) within the FREEDOM study, emphasizing the role of environmental indicators in shaping mental health outcomes. A total of 396 MDD patients were recruited at Policlinico Hospital in Milan, where their clinical severity was assessed through multiple psychiatric rating scales. Exposure to urban greenness was quantified using the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) within a 100-meter radius of their residences, while air pollution levels, specifically fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), were also considered. Statistical models adjusted for demographic and temporal factors revealed that higher levels of urban greenness were consistently associated with a reduction in depressive symptom severity, including improvements in melancholic symptoms, anxiety, and overall functioning. This beneficial effect appeared to be more pronounced in environments with lower PM_{2.5} concentrations, highlighting the interplay between vegetation and air pollution in influencing mental health. The findings suggest that urban greenness has a protective role against severe depression, reinforcing the importance of integrating vegetation into urban planning. Future research should focus on advanced three-dimensional indicators of green space to better capture its volume and potential benefits, further refining our understanding of its impact on mental well-being.

Tree Species Diversity in Urban and Peri-urban Forests Significantly Improved Human Wellbeing in Karlsruhe, southwest Germany

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Abstract

Green spaces and trees are vital components for enhancing human well-being in cities. While the significance of urban greenery for human health is well recognized, the impact of urban biodiversity on well-being remains insufficiently explored in terms of quantitative evidence. This study investigated the relationship between tree genus diversity, perceived urban biodiversity, and the subjective well-being of urban residents in Karlsruhe, Germany. An online questionnaire based on mapping involving 302 participants examined well-being locations and perceptions of biodiversity. Using remote sensing and ground data, tree genus diversity was assessed for nine genera. A novel approach that spatially correlates societal mapping results with tree genus cover maps revealed a distinct preference for green spaces within the constructed urban environment. A significant association was found between the perceived biodiversity of urban green spaces and subjective well-being. The extent of tree cover, the presence of large trees, and the perceived species diversity beyond tree genera all positively contribute to the well-being of the urban population. In contrast, the perceived untidiness of urban areas negatively affects residents' well-being. This should be considered in future research and the design of urban green spaces. To our knowledge, this is one of the first studies worldwide that has quantified and mapped the compositional diversity of urban and peri-urban forests, perceived biodiversity, and human well-being.

BRERA - Wellbeing, Restoration, Resilience, and Adaptation

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Abstract

BRERA represents a transformative urban forestry initiative in Soria, that aligns policy innovation, governance, and planning to create a more resilient city. This project, a collaboration between the Soria City Council, the Natural Heritage Foundation of Castilla y León, and Cesefor, is supported by the Spanish Ministry for Ecological Transition and the EU's NextGenerationEU funds under the Recovery and Resilience Plan.

As a cornerstone of Soria's 2030 Carbon Neutrality Roadmap, BRERA redefines urban planning by integrating green infrastructure to increase biodiversity, enhance resilience to climate change, and foster community well-being. Through the restoration and creation of over 230,000 m² of green spaces, BRERA incorporates 68,000 new plantings, including 7,593 trees, contributing to an annual carbon absorption of 25 tCO₂eq.

The project's holistic approach includes rehabilitating degraded urban areas, creating habitats for pollinators and other species, and implementing green corridors that connect diverse ecosystems. With 20 targeted actions, such as urban ecological corridors, ecological gardens, and reforestation of peri-urban areas, BRERA exemplifies scalable and replicable solutions for integrated urban forest management.

BRERA also establishes a governance model that ensures community engagement throughout its lifecycle, promoting stewardship, accessibility, and inclusivity. Its achievements demonstrate how urban forestry can address climate challenges, improve public health, and bridge policy with practice to create sustainable urban environments.

This contribution will provide insights into BRERA's innovative governance mechanisms, its alignment with Soria's strategic urban planning policies, and its measurable impact on resilience and biodiversity. The presentation will share methodologies, results, and lessons learned, highlighting BRERA as a replicable model for cities aiming to integrate urban forestry into sustainable development strategies.

The Effects of Visits and Types of Activities in Forests close to urban areas on the Subjective Well-being of Visitors during and after the COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

Forests close to urban areas are vital to human well-being, as they provide several ecosystem services including outdoor activities (e.g. recreation) that are crucial for improving mental health. Our study aim is to explore i) the effect of forest activities on the subjective well-being (SWB) of visitors before, during and after COVID-19 pandemic and ii) to evaluate the influence of forest patterns on SWB during and after the pandemic period. In this paper we investigate to what extent various forest activities like (leisure walking, hiking, picking mushroom, picking forest berries and hunting) and the forests appearance and diversity improve visitors' SWB and provide relief from stress, anxiety and depression. Also we examine how forest visit frequency and socio-demographic characteristics influence. This is based on data from a representative (N = 1000) nation-wide digital survey conducted in Slovakia in 2020, and repeated in 2024, to investigate the role of forest restorative effects on SWB and stress induced by the pandemic, under conditions of a strongly limited availability of mental health services, and after societal recovery from the pandemic. One-sample Wilcoxon Signed-rank Test used to assess the deviation of the observed median from the hypothetical neutral value of forest activities and forest features. Multinomial logistic regression and ordinal regression were used to examine impacts of forest activities and forest features on SWB. The results show that forests activities and their features playing the vital role for enhancing mental health and SWB, particularly after pandemic period by explained approximately 13% and 23% of the variability in SWB respectively. We conclude that exposure to forest environment has positive effect on mental health and overall SWB. We recommend policy-makers to rely on these experiences and integrate into forest management practices and strategies, to safeguard the sustainability of the cultural forest ecosystems service.

FRONT PAGE FOR PARALLEL SESSION 3:
URBAN FORESTS FOR INCLUSIVE CITIES

A Methodology to Identify and Prioritize Tree Planting Locations in Urban Areas according to the 3-30-300 rule.

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Abstract

This study presents a GIS-based methodology designed to assist local governments in Limburg, Belgium, in identifying and prioritizing suitable locations for new trees in urban areas, addressing challenges in meeting climate adaptation goals. The methodology builds on the principles of the 3-30-300 rule, which emphasizes the importance of urban greenery for climate resilience and improved living environments.

The method involves extensive preprocessing of geospatial data to delineate plantable areas within public spaces and government-owned parcels. Using a combination of spatial analysis and automation, it identifies zones free from physical and legal constraints where trees can be planted. The process incorporates advanced algorithms to account for existing land cover, height-based object obstructions, and current tree canopy coverage. These steps enable local authorities to systematically evaluate plantable areas while reducing manual efforts.

Building on this foundational analysis, an additional scoring system evaluates potential tree planting sites based on their contribution to the "3-rule" of the 3-30-300 framework, focusing on enhancing tree proximity for buildings within a 25-meter radius. Furthermore, an ongoing refinement of the methodology aims to integrate a scoring system for the "30-rule," assessing the available tree canopy cover within a 500-meter radius of residential areas. This ensures a more comprehensive approach to urban greening, prioritizing locations where tree planting can have the greatest impact on shading, cooling, and biodiversity.

This approach addresses the increasing need for practical tools to optimize urban greening efforts and supports local governments in overcoming challenges related to spatial constraints and resource allocation. The automated and replicable nature of the methodology ensures scalability across municipalities, providing a robust decision-support tool for climate adaptation and sustainable urban planning.

Rethinking Urban Green Space Accessibility Through Route Environment Quality

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Abstract

Urban green spaces (UGS) contribute significantly to public well-being by fostering physical activity and improving mental health. While accessibility is a central concern in UGS planning, conventional approaches often prioritize distance-based metrics, assuming that proximity alone ensures equitable and effective access. However, the environmental conditions along the way to UGS remain largely overlooked, despite their potential to discourage visits and reduce the benefits these spaces offer. This study introduces an environmentally informed accessibility framework by integrating high-resolution environment variables to evaluate the walking routes from residential areas to UGS in Helsinki, Finland. By modeling access to both medium-sized UGS and large UGS, we reveal that routes of similar distance can vary greatly in environmental quality, challenging the assumption that proximity alone guarantees accessibility. Access to larger UGS is particularly affected, reinforcing the need for urban planning strategies that prioritize high-quality pedestrian environments. Beyond identifying spatial disparities, this study proposes a methodological approach that is adaptable to different urban contexts, offering planners tools to assess both UGS distribution and route quality. Our results highlight the limitations of single-dimensional accessibility indicators and advocate for multidimensional measures that account for both distance and route conditions. By integrating environmental quality into accessibility frameworks, cities can create more inclusive, health-promoting urban landscapes that ensure UGS benefits are equitably distributed.

Urban Forest Gardens as a new form of co-created and co-managed urban forests

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Abstract

Urban Forest Gardens can be considered a new type of urban forest, which imitate the structure of a forest with mainly edible plants in several vegetation layers. Apart from ecological benefits that result from its forest-like structure, forest gardens provide a bridge to participatory food production in cities and involve citizens in this multifunctional and long-term form of urban gardening.

In the German Urban Forest Garden Project (Projekt Urbane Waldgärten) three model urban forest gardens were developed in a participatory way since 2019 and implemented since 2021 in different urban areas within the cities of Berlin and Kassel. Each of the urban forest gardens has been co-created by local administrations, associations, citizens and planners, coordinated by the model project team. They are maintained and used by citizen groups in different organizational forms. For all of the model projects the aim is to develop and test new forms of cooperation and governance in a public green space. .

Insights will be given in the project development requirements that can be adapted and transferred to different city contexts, as well as into results from ecological and socio-economic monitoring. While cooling effects are slow to detect, as woody species are still rather small, water regulation improved quickly and the increases in floristic and faunistic biodiversity are surprisingly fast. Also, the development of organizational and inclusive social structures, which have developed together with the forest gardens are promising forms of sustainable urban forest management. The experiences from the model project are different in the three different sites, and hence the project observes these model projects to derive general recommendations for implementation including insights in the main success factors as well as concerning the particular challenges in the management of this special type of urban forest.

Data Driven Design: Systematic Approaches to Urban Forest Planning

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Abstract

Systemic challenges to the urban forest require systemic solutions, ones equitable and resilient in the face of changing demographics and climate patterns. This presentation builds upon a high-level meta-analysis of data-driven urban forest planning studies around the world to identify the key analytical tools that are necessary to diagnose the unique conditions and potential for each city and to propose integrated strategies for growing a healthier and more resilient urban forest.

This analysis was conducted as part of a research-seminar at Harvard's Department of Landscape Architecture and integrates perspectives of planning, design, and urban forest management.

The research has uncovered a series of common components to effective urban forest planning.

ROBUST ANALYTICAL TOOLS

Assessing historical canopy change through LiDAR or multi-spectral photography enables a community to understand underlying trends and to prioritize efforts at change. Correlating loss or gain with land use type and ownership, development patterns, and demographic data enables planners to pin-point pathologies that underly local dynamics and to direct resources equitably and efficiently.

TARGETED STRATEGIES

Forest-stewardship and forest-building strategies are organized in four key categories: Design, because the cities of tomorrow will look different than those of the past to support sufficient canopy; Policy, because regulatory frameworks make slow and steady change across all property types; Advocacy, because engaging a skeptical public is more than just education; and Practice, because on-the-ground tactics are key to tree establishment and flourishing.

This presentation will identify opportunities to overcome analytical bottlenecks and advance data-driven urban forest planning. We will also contemplate future directions in planning practice and opportunities for cross-disciplinary strategies to enable healthier forests and healthier cities worldwide.

Urban forestry citizen science and community-based stewardship in Birmingham - the UK's second largest city.

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Abstract

As metropolitan regions of Europe develop pathways to climate resilience, sustainable urban forests are crucial to help cities adapt to climate hazards such as surface water flooding and extreme heat. Generally, the larger a tree canopy, the greater the ecosystem services provided; however, trees must first survive their 'early years' and grow big before they can begin delivering these well-documented ecosystem services.

The city of Birmingham, UK, is a Biophilic City (2014), a Tree City of World (since 2019) and the first UK city to adopt an 'Urban Forest Master Plan.' Birmingham has a comprehensive, geospatially mapped street tree inventory, which has facilitated an ambitious large-scale, long-term project since 2020 between Birmingham TreePeople (a Non-Governmental Organisation), the University of Birmingham, and Birmingham City Council.

This citizen science-led research explores i) tree establishment data for street trees 3-, 5- and 9-years after planting and ii) how strong links between trees, people, and communities can be achieved through community-stewardship. The methodological approach to date has required carefully trained volunteers, who have surveyed over 3000 street trees that were planted between 2015 and 2020 across Birmingham. The 'Planted Tree Re-Inventory Protocol' (Vogt et al, 2014) is used, resulting in detailed information about each surveyed tree - including measurements of tree growth, health and social-ecological growing conditions. Volunteers also provide some 'tender loving care' (stewardship) to each surveyed tree such as removing or readjusting any tree protection (tree stakes and ties), and they actively engage with local residents.

Initial results will be shared including tree mortality rates and lessons learnt from working with volunteers on the project.

Challenges and enabling factors of participation in the transition process towards a Biocity: learnings from Switzerland

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Abstract

Urban areas are confronted with simultaneous challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, public health emergencies, and exponential urbanization. In order to create livable, healthy and resilient urban environments a paradigm change in urban planning and design is needed. In response to it, the European Forest Institute developed the concept of Biocities which presents a holistic vision of a sustainable city. Citizens are regarded as key players in the transition to Biocities and thus, participation is a key component. This study aims to identify challenges and enabling factors of participation in the transition process towards a Biocity. To do so, we conducted desk-research, a workshop and seven expert interviews in 2024, with practitioners involved in Biocity related projects. The projects are set in the Swiss cities Zurich, Winterthur, and St. Gallen which experience continued population growth. The results reveal that it is important to develop a common understanding of participation within a democratic system among public and private actors to enable a transition to a Biocity. The enabling factors derived include transparent communication concerning competences of participating stakeholders, the need of adequate resources that allow participation, creating visions that people can relate to, as well as to ensure skillful and experienced facilitation of the participation process. The main challenges identified are the existing boundary conditions to comply with the legal system, the complex structures of city administrations, the administration's reluctance to support projects initiated by citizens, and hindering political debates sparked by participation processes. Interviewees and workshop participants emphasized the importance of citizen participation in the implementation of Biocity related projects. These insights underline the necessity of fostering inclusive and well-structured participation processes to facilitate the transition to Biocities.

From Community to Commodity: Contestations over Space in the Making of Somali Enclaves in Nairobi's Pumwani-Majengo

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Abstract

This paper explores how competing interests shape the appropriation and contestation of green spaces within informal settlements. Using Nairobi's Pumwani-Majengo informal settlement as a case study, we employ the Urban Political Ecology (UPE) framework as a lens and adopt a mixed-methods approach—incorporating data from interviews, expert consultations, field observations, and archival and spatial analyses—to provide a comprehensive analysis of these dynamics. Our findings reveal that displacement in Pumwani-Majengo disrupts social, cultural, and economic networks. Residents respond by resigning, resisting, negotiating, or advocating. Greening and ungreening coincide, are often politicised, and selectively implemented, affecting vulnerable groups. Lastly, land transformation goes along with the formation of socioeconomic enclaves, which leads to the fragmentation of neighbourhoods into zones, favouring wealthier newcomers, while further marginalising low-income residents. These findings, we argue, challenge the conventional view of urban green spaces as public goods, exposing their co-optation for elite-driven aesthetic and commercial purposes. In sum, we offer insights for future urban sustainability initiatives and environmental agendas in African cities, contributing to broader debates on urban green space development and contestation.

Keywords: Land politics, enclaves, greening and ungreening, displacement, power dynamics, informal settlements

UK urban forests and the 3-30-300 rule

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Abstract

In the UK, cities are pushing for higher tree canopy cover, but does this bring an improvement in access to trees and greenspaces? Canopy cover estimates are valuable tools for measuring and monitoring changes in existing tree cover, but these percentages don't tell us how trees, and their benefits, are distributed across an area.

Despite an abundance of work evaluating access to trees and greenspaces, there is no standard tool for measuring this, and so it is difficult to compare access across locations. Many measurements rely on tree canopy cover but do not consider the spread and accessibility of trees across an area. The 3-30-300 rule offers a straightforward standard to examine access to trees and greenspaces and in addition to canopy cover, the distribution of trees around people's homes, schools and workplaces is considered.

The 3-30-300 rule is gaining popularity elsewhere in Europe, but not yet in the UK. We measure the 3-30-300 rule in the local authority areas of 7 English cities, examining how overall canopy cover and where the canopy is situated (e.g. woodland, street, private garden) impact success. This can be used to inform urban tree planning; ensuring that existing and newly planted trees are accessible and providing maximum benefits to the population.

We also explore how sensitive the results of the 3-30-300 analysis are to several methodological choices. We compare a buffer method to a method using a network of walking routes for the '300' rule and find that in each city region approximately twice as many buildings are within 300 m of a greenspace for the buffer method compared to the network analysis. Comparison of a buffer and a simulation of window lines of sight for the '3' rule in the same regions shows that the fraction of buildings from which three trees are visible is reduced by around 10 % using lines of sight. These results indicate that methods should be chosen carefully to meet the desired outcomes of applying the 3-30-300 rule.

Differences in perceived health benefits and travel distances to green space across population groups: Insights from a Public Participation GIS study

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Abstract

Despite the growing evidence base linking urban green space access to human health and well-being, questions remain about the optimal properties, quantity, and location of health-supportive functions within green infrastructure. These challenges are particularly evident in efforts to integrate health and well-being perspectives into green infrastructure planning and management, where access to any green space is often assumed to translate into health benefits. However, prior research suggests that specific green space properties influence different health outcomes, indicating that health-supportive functions are not evenly distributed across green infrastructure.

This study draws on distributional justice literature and employs a spatial-analytical approach to assess the demand for and access to specific green space health benefits. Primary data on urban green space use in the Vienna Metropolitan Area, Austria, were collected using Public Participation GIS (PPGIS), a digital participatory mapping method. Adult participants (N = 1,723) marked frequently visited green spaces on a base map (N = 5,882) and evaluated each site based on its building, restoring, and harm-reducing capacities. In-group differences in distances to visited green spaces and perceived health benefits were analyzed using logistic regression models and visualized with Kernel density plots.

The results revealed distinct patterns in the health benefits associated with actual green space use, reflecting both varying demands for health-supportive functions among different population groups and disparities in their distribution across urban green infrastructure. Overall, the findings suggest that systematic spatial monitoring of health-supportive green space functions can identify inequities in green space access and could enhance the integration of health and well-being perspectives into multifunctional green infrastructure planning.

From the inactive to the multi-tasker: insights from a large Dutch survey into individual and collective efforts in green volunteering

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Abstract

Citizens are nowadays recognized as key actors in addressing societal challenges. Their engagement fosters collective responsibility, strengthens democratic processes, and enhances policy. In nature conservation, citizen involvement is important for integrating nature into other domains of life, contributing to biodiversity and the quality of life. However, the lack of representative data on who these volunteers are, what activities they engage in, and how they contribute hinders long-term monitoring and policy development. Current data primarily focus on organizational volunteers, overlooking many citizens who act individually or form informal initiatives. Understanding these diverse forms of engagement is essential for supporting citizen-led conservation efforts.

A representative online survey of 10,779 Dutch adults identified four groups: individual volunteers (22%), those in professional organizations (4%), community initiative volunteers (8%), and non-volunteers (66%). Volunteers were generally higher educated and more likely to live in greener areas. Common activities included litter collection (73%), nature monitoring (28%), and maintaining public green (25%). Motivations extended beyond environmental concerns to enjoyment, outdoor experiences, and physical activity. For potential volunteers, flexibility, proximity, and access to information were key motivators.

The study highlights differences between volunteer groups and emphasizes the need to look beyond organizational volunteers. Individual volunteers, the largest group, engage flexibly but less intensively. Community initiative volunteers are locally focused and socially driven, while professional organization volunteers participate in a broader range of activities. These insights help policymakers and organizations better support volunteer engagement in nature conservation, emphasizing both ecological and social benefits. Ongoing monitoring is needed to track trends and adapt strategies over time.

Multifaceted green areas and forests in changing cities: insights for a socio-ecological evaluation improvement

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Abstract

Urban green spaces (UGS) are continuously developed around the world to deliver multiple benefits. Among UGS, urban forests (UF) planning may be driven by a broad range of benefits such as the need for climate change adaptation, the preservation and creation of habitats, or to enhance people's connection to nature. Socio-ecological research on UF inherently embraces an interdisciplinary approach to provide insight into cities multidimensional patterns and processes. But the miss-matching between social and ecological observations can create ambiguity in the development and use of clear indicators for sustainable planning. We present an interdisciplinary reflection on socio-ecological research of UF to investigate the socio-cultural dimension in a more epistemologically and methodologically accurate manner respect to the current literature. Indeed, this latter suffers from some important gaps concerning a) lack of balanced engagement of colleagues from different fields; b) limited time to explore new approaches due to research-related time constraints; c) lack of qualitative bottom-up approaches; d) fully integrated analysis of socio-ecological data. Starting from the essential background information, we propose that the system itself should inform methodological approaches with the aim to avoid over-reductionist research and top-down production of knowledge. Moreover, as socio-ecological systems are highly dynamic, the use of multiple spatial and temporal scales can help in strengthening socio-ecological evidence. The implementation of a combined set of socio-ecological variables and indicators within a clear interdisciplinary and bottom-up methodological framework should help in improving future socio-ecological studies and enhance their comparability across cities. We therefore call for an improved understanding of the benefits of socio-ecological approaches, bringing people together to share their knowledge and develop further common protocols.

CommuniTree - Tea under trees: promoting urban green spaces through community engagement

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Abstract

Urban areas are often dominated by concrete and asphalt, creating heat islands, while municipal budgets for green spaces remain limited. The CommuniTree project encourages collaboration between the municipality and local communities to increase urban green space. Neighbourhoods can plant and maintain trees in unused areas such as old orchards with public support, but often lack the link - a contact person at the city.

In the small town of Freising, Germany, the project, which started in January 2025, is a joint effort between the University of Weihenstephan-Triesdorf, the non-profit organisation Rekulvistas and committed citizens. One of the main objectives is the participatory expansion of urban green spaces, combining scientific research with community action. With the help of a new citizen science app, students and citizens will help to map the city's tree population.

City officials, citizens and students will come together in workshops to identify potential planting areas according to the 3:30:300 principle and plan planting campaigns where the requirements of this rule are not fulfilled. Where there are no suitable areas, trees will be planted in pots in the city centre to temporarily simulate a greener environment before being planted on the green campus of Freising University.

To involve the population, the project will also organise 'tea under trees' events - low-threshold gatherings where the city trees are celebrated with artistic activities and communal tea drinking, e.g. lime blossom tea. Students will evaluate the effectiveness of the participation formats and also assess newly planted trees to compare species, planting methods and growth with trees planted by experts.

Want to find out more? Take part in a CommuniTee event in Zurich and be inspired!

Would you walk here? Urban wildscapes as visual settings for utility and recreational walks

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Abstract

Walking is a primary physical activity that connects city inhabitants with nature, contributing to the development of healthy and sustainable cities. While green walking environments are typically associated with manicured urban parks and street greenery, other potential settings include urban wildscapes.

Urban wildscapes are visually 'natural' or even 'wild' green spaces, shaped primarily by nature, characterised by spontaneous vegetation and minimal human intervention. These areas typically feature unmaintained greenery with high biodiversity, contributing to the reconnection of fragmented urban habitats. They are closely tied to the concept of wildness, referring to the extent of spontaneous vegetation growth and biodiversity enhancement.

This study explores whether city inhabitants are willing to walk through urban wildscapes and the factors influencing this willingness. Our novelty lies in demonstrating how 'wild' green spaces can be integrated into urban landscapes to promote walkability. We move beyond the green spaces traditionally associated with city walking activities and focus on how urban wildscapes – characterised by unmaintained, overgrown or spontaneous greenery – can support or limit city inhabitants' willingness to walk.

We surveyed 524 residents of Warsaw, Poland, assessing their willingness to walk through eighteen urban wildscapes for both utility and recreational purposes. City inhabitants preferred scattered greenery and grasslands for utility walks, while dense greenery and forests were favoured for recreational walks. A broader acceptance of walking through urban wildscapes could reduce the costs of maintaining urban green spaces and provide ecological benefits by preserving these areas in their 'wild' state. These findings contribute to discussions on social-ecological connectivity and the need to consider 'nature of the fourth kind' when planning green corridors that address societal and environmental needs

FRONT PAGE FOR PARALLEL SESSION 4:
URBAN FORESTS FOR SUSTAINABLE URBAN
PLANNING

Session 4 - Urban Forests for Sustainable Urban Planning

Challenges and Solutions in Measuring Urban Trees in the City Environment

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Abstract

Measuring urban trees in the city presents unique challenges that require specific approaches to monitoring. Key issues include limited access to suitable measurement locations, external disturbances such as vandalism, and difficult environmental conditions like soil compaction, irregular water availability, and high air pollution. These factors can significantly affect measurement accuracy and call into question the reliability of results.

One common problem is unauthorized interference with monitoring systems, such as the theft of data loggers, which jeopardizes data quality. To prevent such incidents, vandalism-resistant systems and close collaboration with local stakeholders, including authorities and residents, are essential. This can enhance the security of the devices and ensure their functionality over the long term.

Furthermore, the specific conditions of urban environments require adapted measurement methodologies. The impact of air pollution, traffic, and extreme weather conditions can compromise measurement accuracy. Redundant measurement systems, regular maintenance of equipment, and the use of alternative technologies, such as drones or non-invasive methods, can help maintain data quality despite these disturbances.

Another challenge when measuring urban trees is the heterogeneous soil structure and the variety of factors influencing tree vitality. To obtain reliable data, interdisciplinary approaches are necessary, considering both the technical measurements and the social and spatial context.

This contribution will compare and evaluate experiences and lessons-learned from several countries and research projects in the field of urban forestry and blue-green infrastructures. Recommendations for communication concepts, comparable and robust measurement methods will be derived from this and put up for discussion.

Management Strategies for Urban Trees in Lisbon: Addressing Decay Fungi and Enhancing Urban Tree Health

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Abstract

According to Lisbon's tree cover inventory, there are approximately 60,000 street trees in the municipality. The majority of these trees are mature individuals, with diameters at breast height (DBH) ranging between 0.40 m and 0.60 m. Trees are essential components of modern cities, providing numerous benefits. However, they are subjected to various abiotic and biotic stresses. One of the major concerns for urban tree managers is decay fungi, which can render trees hazardous. Timely detection and identification of these fungi are crucial for developing appropriate management strategies.

In this study, samples of decay fungi were collected from various species of urban trees in Lisbon and identified based on macroscopic features of the basidiomata, as well as cultural and molecular characterisation. *Inonotus rickii* was one of the most frequently found fungal species, followed by *Ganoderma adspersum* and *G. resinaceum*. Phylogenetic analyses revealed low intraspecific genetic variability among the populations of these wood rot fungi.

Additionally, trees hosting these wood rot fungi were analysed for the associated risk of failure using the Visual Tree Assessment (VTA) method. Both *I. rickii* and *Ganoderma* spp. significantly impact the mechanical stability of the trees they infect. Specifically, the failure of European hackberry, linden, and poplar trees appears to be related to the presence of these fungi in the city.

Based on the spatial distribution of *I. rickii* and *Ganoderma* spp. and their primary host trees, a management plan is proposed to help the municipality improve the quality of urban tree cover while minimising phytosanitary problems and community impacts.

Transforming Urban Forest Monitoring through Gamified Augmented Reality

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Abstract

Urban forests face growing challenges due to climate change and urbanisation, necessitating innovative approaches to environmental monitoring. This research explores gamified augmented reality (AR) technologies as a novel means of engaging citizens in urban forest mapping through a comparative study in Finland and Japan.

Our interdisciplinary study examines how different gameful AR interactions can motivate mobile phone users to collect environmental data across cultural contexts. Using LiDAR-equipped smartphones, interactive AR experiences were used to collect forest point cloud and mesh data while participants engaged in playing with spider-catching and space probe retrieval games, as well as spray painting and point cloud pixelation experiences.

Findings highlight the potential of gamified approaches to facilitate environmental data collection across different interaction scenarios. Preliminary analyses from workshops conducted in urban forests in Finland and Japan suggest cultural differences in user engagement and interaction preferences, with noticeable variations in how users interact with and generate point clouds across the different game designs. By tracking phone movement and angle during data collection, user navigation paths were visualised as linear trajectories within point cloud representations, providing insights into the effects of different gamification strategies on spatial exploration.

This approach presents an opportunity for urban forestry planning. AR tools can engage citizens in forest monitoring and assist forestry professionals. Ultimately, this could lead to the creation of digital twins of urban forests that can be analysed in virtual reality by professionals, policymakers, and the public. In this way, gamification and AR technologies can transform participatory planning processes and enhance the work of urban forestry practitioners.

Investigating the Water Sources of Urban Trees

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Abstract

Urban trees play a vital role in resilient cities, providing essential ecosystem services such as cooling, carbon sequestration, and improved air quality. However, their ability to deliver these benefits depends on their resilience to urban stressors like limited rooting space, water scarcity, elevated temperatures, and anthropogenic activity. Understanding their hydraulic strategies and water uptake dynamics is therefore crucial for supporting effective urban planning and management.

This study aimed to investigate the water uptake depth of urban trees in Zurich, Switzerland, using stable water isotope analysis. In 2024, nearly 90 deciduous trees were sampled at street and park locations. *Prunus* and *Acer* trees were studied along an urban density gradient to assess Urban Heat Island (UHI) effects on water uptake. Additionally, *Quercus*, *Alnus*, and *Tilia* trees were sampled to examine interspecies variations under similar environmental conditions. Soil and twig samples were processed using cryogenic water extraction, and Oxygen and hydrogen isotopic composition of the aqueous samples were measured using an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (IRMS). A Bayesian mixing model attributed soil water sources from various depths to xylem samples. Sampling occurred three times during the growing season to capture potential phenological effects.

Preliminary results reveal significant differences in water uptake depths between *Prunus* and *Acer*. For *Prunus*, water uptake depth increased with urban density, indicating possible effects of UHI on tree hydraulic strategies. These findings suggest trees in UHI affected areas may adapt by developing deeper roots to access water.

Expanding our database with additional years and complementary measurements, our findings will inform strategies to enhance the resilience and sustainability of urban green spaces, ensuring that trees can continue to play a vital role in mitigating climate risks and improving urban living conditions.

Greening Ejisu: Urban Forests for Sustainable Cities

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Abstract

Urban forests are essential for fostering sustainable and resilient cities by mitigating climate impacts, enhancing biodiversity, and improving community well-being. This paper presents a pilot initiative titled "Greening Ejisu," led by Earth Care Ghana in partnership with the Ghana Seed Centre. The project aims to integrate urban forests into Ejisu's urban planning framework by creating multifunctional green spaces with native tree species sourced from the Ghana Seed Centre.

A core aspect of this initiative is community engagement, involving local residents, schools, and organizations in tree planting, maintenance, and advocacy. By empowering the community through education and participatory approaches, the project fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility for the urban environment.

This pilot also emphasizes sustainable practices, including climate-resilient tree selection, nursery establishment, and ongoing monitoring to ensure long-term success. Additionally, the project advocates for policy integration, encouraging local authorities to prioritize urban forestry in urban development plans.

Greening Ejisu serves as a replicable model for urban forestry across Ghana, demonstrating how community-driven efforts can transform urban landscapes, enhance environmental sustainability, and promote social equity. This case study highlights the potential of urban forests as a critical tool for addressing urbanization challenges and achieving sustainable development goals.

First results from the Urban Trees Ecophysiology Network (UTEN)

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Abstract

This abstract is behalf of all members of the Urban Tree Ecophysiology Network (UTEN) - <https://www.uten-network.com/>

With ongoing urbanization, most of the global population now lives in cities, facing various environmental stressors. Urban areas can be up to 10°C warmer than nearby rural areas due to energy use and infrastructure. This urban heat intensifies the challenges posed by climate change and population growth. Increasing tree canopy cover is a powerful tool to enhance urban life, providing benefits like reduced energy consumption, lower temperatures through shading and transpiration, pollution mitigation, and improved well-being. However, urban trees face challenges from abiotic and biotic stressors, especially due to climate change, which threaten their cooling potential and overall ecosystem services. Understanding the relationship between urban settings and tree ecophysiology is vital for climate adaptation and urban forest health.

To address these issues, the Urban Tree Ecophysiology Network (UTEN) was formed, connecting researchers, stakeholders, and municipalities globally. UTEN focuses on how urban environments affect tree health and how trees influence city microclimates across different biomes. Using a campaign-based approach and IoT sensors, the network measures tree transpiration, growth, and changes in diameter, along with temperature and humidity. Seasonal physiological data also inform tree health assessments. This shared data helps researchers tackle common issues regarding tree health and stress in urban climates, while also addressing site-specific questions.

UTEN, uniting 16 cities worldwide, promotes international collaboration and data sharing to optimize urban tree ecosystems. In my presentation, I will discuss preliminary findings from a 2 years of measurements, offering early insights and conclusions to guide future urban sustainability efforts.

Rewilding cities for climate and ecological resilience: a comparative study of Delhi and Milan

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Abstract

Urban forests are often seen as mere green spaces in cities, yet they play a much deeper role as living ecosystems that provide essential services for both people and the environment. Their potential as active carbon sinks, biodiversity hotspots, and climate resilience tools remains underutilised. This paper explores rewilding-based urban forestry strategies that go beyond tree planting to embrace assisted natural regeneration (ANR), species conservation, and diversified canopy structures that enhance carbon sequestration and ecological restoration. Through an analysis of two distinct urban forest initiatives—Delhi’s Aravalli Biodiversity Park (India), a community-led effort to revive native landscapes, and Milan’s Forestami project (Tiny Forests), promoted by local public authorities—we demonstrate how urban forests can be designed, managed, and scaled differently while contributing to urban resilience and well-being. The Delhi case exemplifies grassroots ecological restoration, where local communities reclaim degraded land and transform it into thriving forests, while Milan’s project highlights the potential of collaborative investment in greening compact urban spaces. Both cases show that urban forests are not just passive green infrastructure—they are dynamic ecosystems that absorb carbon, support wildlife, improve air quality, and enhance the quality of life in polluted localities. Our findings suggest the need for integrated urban policies that merge biodiversity conservation, carbon storage, and resilient urban planning, fostering partnerships between local communities, municipalities, and private entities. By embracing a collaborative approach, cities can rewild urban landscapes, reconnect people with nature, and create sustainable, climate-resilient environments for future generations.

The potential of biodiversity effects of native and non-native species in urban ecosystems under climate warming

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Abstract

The planting of trees as a nature based solution in urban heat islands is a key strategy to mitigate climate warming effects. However, whereas the question on the planting of native vs. non-native species is intensively debated, the physiological differences between tree species and the combination of species to maximise diversity effects and urban ecosystem services is still rarely considered. To allow an evidence-based planning of urban green infrastructure, we used drone remote sensing techniques to assess differences in cooling potential of mature trees grown under identical environmental conditions in Rapperswil, Switzerland. We detected significant differences in canopy surface temperature among individual tree species correlated with morphological leaf traits. Based on these results, we discuss how thermal mapping and landscape design might benefit from diversity effects based on plant functional traits.

Urban and peri-urban monumental trees as biodiversity hubs: an international study across Grenoble (France), Helsinki and Espoo (Finland), and the Veneto region (Italy)

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Abstract

Urban and peri-urban trees and forests are increasingly recognized as valuable components of landscape settings for biodiversity conservation. Among them, monumental trees stand out as significant elements in urban settings. Monumental trees, characterized by distinct size, shape, and age, stand out for their significant ecological, landscape and cultural values. Therefore, monumental trees require targeted management and planning measures to protect their unique contributions. In this study, we aim to identify, analyze, and describe monumental tree communities, focusing on their biodiversity and ecological roles. We compared three study areas: the Veneto region (Italy), the city of Grenoble (France), and the cities of Espoo and Helsinki (Finland). Through the survey of tree-related microhabitats (TreMs) on 499 monumental trees, we investigated the biodiversity potential provided by monumental trees in urban areas across three European countries along an environmental gradient. We found a large variety of TreMs types across the analyzed monumental tree community. On average (\pm s.d.), this community hosts a TreMs richness of 5.5 ± 3.7 with regional variation (Veneto: 5.5 ± 3.6 ; Grenoble: 4.8 ± 3.3 ; Espoo: 7.8 ± 3.4 ; Helsinki: 4.9 ± 4.7). Among them, crown microsoil and bryophytes stood out as the most prevalent TreMs, found in 56% and 51% of monumental trees, respectively. This project seeks to improve understanding of urban monumental tree communities by highlighting their ecological roles, thereby advancing conservation efforts for these exceptional individuals. In this context, surveying tree-related microhabitats is a promising approach for studying the multifaced biodiversity support provided by monumental trees.

Professionals' perceptions of and attitudes towards public participation in planning and management of urban trees, forests and green space

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Abstract

An online survey of 582 professionals was conducted in 10 European countries. It addressed various aspects of planning and management related to trees, forests and green space in urban areas. The goal of the study was to explore a) what attitudes the professionals have towards public involvement in various activities related to trees, forests and green space, b) what advantages and challenges of public participation they perceive, c) what traits they value in potential volunteers, and d) how professionals' sociodemographic characteristics influence their attitudes and perceptions. The results show that professionals were most supportive of public participation in activities such as monitoring incivilities, raising awareness and campaigning, or litter picking. On the other hand, the least supported activities were participation in tree assessments, monitoring of tree pests, diseases and invasive alien species, and tree inventories. Professionals agreed that public participation helps raise awareness among participants on the importance of managing trees, forests, and green space, makes people more attached to these resources, and builds trust between the public and professionals. The biggest perceived challenges to public participation were the lack of human capacities among professionals and the lack of political will to involve the public. The most desirable trait of the potential volunteers was the willingness to learn, while former experience in similar activities was the least important. Professionals' country of origin and gender affected their perceptions and attitudes the most. The results are relevant for both the scientific community since the study was conducted in countries that are less present in the scientific literature on the topic, and practitioners, who are often under pressure to involve the public for various reasons but often lack the capacities to do so (properly).

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Abstract

Grünes Gallustal serves as a pioneering framework to advance sustainability and enhance the quality of life in the city of St. Gallen, Switzerland. Developed through a bottom-up approach led by civil society, this initiative presents 14 carefully designed planning measures aimed at climate adaptation, biodiversity enhancement, and urban improvement. The measures range in complexity, from small-scale interventions such as tree planting and the reversal of soil sealing, to larger urban projects, including watercourse restoration and highway capping. Each measure is supported by clear, measurable sub-objectives.

This 1,500-page blueprint is the outcome of a three-year, interdisciplinary collaboration involving 20 experts, incorporating rigorous scientific analyses, climate maps, and detailed before-and-after visualizations thus offering the public tangible perspectives on the city's potential. Initial pilot projects in the city's east, such as the Areal Bach and the "Edible Park" in Stephanshorn, have already been successfully implemented, demonstrating the feasibility and positive impact of the proposed strategies. The city administration and political stakeholders have endorsed the blueprint, establishing Grünes Gallustal as an influential, though informal, green master plan.

Inspired by innovative urban planning models from cities such as Medellín, Vienna, and London, this blueprint promotes an integrated approach that blends urban planning, landscape architecture, and architecture. Its emphasis on low-barrier citizen participation highlights a commitment to fostering broad public acceptance and engagement. As Switzerland's first published comprehensive green urban planning concept, Grünes Gallustal offers a scalable, adaptable framework that can address urban challenges across Switzerland and beyond.

Bridging Technology and Citizen Engagement in Urban Forestry

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Abstract

Urban forests are vital for climate resilience and urban well-being, yet balancing ecological, social, and economic goals remains challenging. Limited resources, fragmented communication, and complex citizen engagement hinder effective decision-making. Digital solutions enhance transparency, streamline management, and foster citizen participation in urban forest governance.

Modern cloud and mobile technologies facilitate information sharing, field coordination, and community engagement. Integrating these tools into existing workflows boosts efficiency without disrupting administrative structures.

Key advancements include digitalizing information sharing and operational management. Citizen engagement benefits from crowdsourcing and digital participation platforms. Accessible tools, like map-based applications, enable residents to provide feedback, report observations, and contribute to urban forest planning, fostering two-way communication and transparency. Real-time reporting from field workers reduces administrative burdens and improves response times.

Practical solutions to these challenges already exist and crowdsourcing has already been used in cities and projects to collect citizens' preferences and perceptions for urban green governance. Studies like "Whose park? Crowdsourcing citizen's urban green space preferences to inform needs-based management decisions" and "Crowdsourcing Public Engagement for Urban Planning in the Global South" highlight how digital methods enhance participation and data collection for decision-making.

Leveraging technology makes urban forest governance more inclusive, data-driven, and adaptable to evolving environmental and societal needs. Digital tools increase transparency, optimise task coordination, and support sustainable urban forest management.

A Spatially Explicit Approach for Optimizing Urban Afforestation to Achieve Project Goals

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Abstract

Urban forests provide essential ecosystem services, support native biodiversity, and advance to sustainable development goals. The benefits provided are often influenced by the forest's configuration within the urban landscape matrix, emphasizing the importance of increasing tree cover in strategic locations. Despite increasing investments in urban tree planting initiatives, many projects lack a systematic, data-driven approach for prioritizing planting locations and assessing their ecological and socioeconomic impacts. This gap limits practitioners' ability to develop urban afforestation plans that balance spatial availability, resource limitations, and competing project goals.

In this study we introduce a spatially explicit tool designed to identify optimal tree planting sites within urban environments based on specific goals or desired outcomes. The tool's algorithm analyzes high-resolution geospatial data to identify and rank viable planting locations, simulate afforestation scenarios, and integrate external programs to quantify potential outcomes. The tool produces a detailed inventory of the number of trees that can be planted in any given city, along with actionable information including the geographic coordinates of each site and the maximum size tree that can be accommodated in each. By using this information to quantify specific outcomes, such as ecosystem service provisioning or impacts to native biodiversity, users can evaluate whether the project's goals are achievable and which planting strategy is most effective. Furthermore, the precise number and location of planting sites can be incorporated to strengthen long-term management plans and resiliency efforts.

This presentation will feature case studies from the US and Europe to assess the impacts of different urban afforestation strategies, and demonstrate the tool's potential to strengthen urban tree planting efforts across the world

FRONT PAGE: POSTERS PRESENTATION:

Chair: **Rik De Vreese** (European Forest Institute and member of 2024/2025 EFUF Board)

A comparison of priorities and interests of practitioners and researchers

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Abstract

Creating and maintaining a biodiverse and resilient urban forest is a major challenge for practitioners and researchers alike. While the mission is the same, researchers and practitioners do not always have the same interests and priorities, due to different working realities and incentive structures. This can lead to different priorities when it comes to developing and adapting planning and management of urban green. Motivated by this potential disparity, we organized the workshop 'Re-thinking how urban trees can help us living in harmony with nature' in November 2024. Among the 55 participants, there were 30 practitioners and 25 scientists from Switzerland and other European countries (e.g., Germany, Italy, UK).

Before the workshop, we used the 2030 targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity framework to identify key topics within the field of urban green. Building on this, we designed a questionnaire, which was sent out to the workshop participants beforehand. Through the questionnaire, participants indicated their topic preferences, which were used to shape the workshop agenda and as a basis for discussion. This structured questionnaire allowed us to compare priorities and interests of researchers and practitioners.

The results of the questionnaire revealed some striking differences: researchers perceived human well-being as well as spread of invasive species as more relevant than practitioners did. However, both groups agreed that climate change and habitat conservation and restoration were the most important topics. In this presentation we will show and discuss the results of the questionnaire in more detail and present the main open research questions identified at the workshop.

Researchers can use the identified research questions to aid relevant and impactful innovation in urban green planning and management. The answers to these questions could be used by practitioners to create and maintain biodiverse and resilient urban forests.

Green governance innovation in the city of Soria: How the application of smart technologies and citizen participation tools improve urban governance for the management of green spaces in Soria

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Abstract

In the city of Soria (Spain), a medium-size city with a population of 40,000 inhabitants, the City Council has promoted the participatory process called Soria 2030, based on the transition management approach at the urban scale, with the main objective of developing a Roadmap to guide the city towards climate neutrality by 2030. For this purpose, tools provided by EIT Climate-KIC have been widely applied in systemic innovation and transition management combined with other project management and innovation instruments. Community commitment has been essential to bring concrete and innovative solutions to some of the greatest challenges to accelerate the green and digital transformation. In this framework, arises BRERA - Wellness, Restoration, Resilience and Adaptation- a project which has the support of the Biodiversity Foundation of the Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, financed by the EU - NextGenerationEU. This project aims to create 179,927 m² of new green areas and restore 50,067 m² of currently degraded spaces at the local level, absorbing 24.25 tons of CO₂/year. BRERA seeks to consolidate a model of innovative and inclusive governance and invite all local population to take an active role by designing, monitoring and taking care of all these new natural and green spaces. Participation is facilitated throughout a Citizen Science Mobile Application where citizens can record geolocated observations and provide detailed information of urban flora and fauna. The GIS data website is an advanced geospatial data management and analysis platform to visualize and analyze the impact of BRERA. Both, the Citizen Science App and the GIS data website, are key tools to facilitate data collection and analysis, to promote environmental education and green local transformation. This study explores how smart city technology governance innovations can address key issues and promote integrated and sustainable urban forest management

Enhancing Resilience through Agroforestry: A green corridor along the Northern Marmara Highway

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Abstract

This research aims to enhance resilience in Istanbul's urban ecological and sociological systems by using agroforestry systems to mitigate the impacts of the Northern Marmara Highway (NMH) on agricultural lands.

The Northern Marmara Highway (NMH) is one of the most significant factors threatening and destroying the Istanbul Northern Forests and rural areas. The infrastructure of this highway passes through 137 kilometers of forest areas, 132 kilometers of agricultural lands, and 33 kilometers of pasturelands and water basins, causing significant damage to these areas. This destruction has disrupted the ecological integrity of rural areas, weakened connections, and transformed green spaces into isolated islands (KORU Istanbul Strategy Document, 2023). Additionally, the infrastructure provided by the highway threatens the sociological structure of rural areas. In the future, it could encourage rural-to-urban migration, significantly reducing traditional economic activities such as agriculture and livestock. The damage and threats caused by this infrastructure may deepen in the future with the increasing effects of climate change.

In this context, applying agroforestry systems along the agricultural lands of the highway route to reduce the impacts of the Northern Marmara Highway would be a beneficial solution. These systems provide benefits such as strengthening ecosystem services, reducing carbon emissions, diversifying local food production, increasing biodiversity, and mitigating drought. This study seeks to utilize these benefits while simultaneously integrating agroforestry systems into the city's green infrastructure. In doing so, the ecological and sociological connections between rural and urban areas will be strengthened.

In conclusion, this research will present a study that evaluates the potential of agroforestry systems along the Northern Marmara Highway and how these systems can be integrated into green corridors to enhance ecosystem services.

Radiation modelling as a first step into a numerical simulation of energy and CO₂ exchanges between plants and the urban atmosphere

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Abstract

Urbanization impacts Earth's systems by increasing CO₂ emissions, creating Urban Heat Islands (UHI), and affecting climate, energy use, and public health. Understanding urban microclimates, energy and CO₂ balances is crucial for climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies and therefore to improve urban resilience. This study presents a radiation model, which is a first step for the development of a 3D microscale model for CO₂, water, and energy exchanges between trees and the urban atmosphere.

Using high-resolution Digital Surface Models (DSMs), land cover data, and Leaf Area Index (LAI), a 3D urban landscape is constructed with isometric voxels categorized as buildings, trees, terrain, or empty. A ray-tracing algorithm calculates parameters like Sky View Factor (SVF) and light transmission coefficients for tree canopies, enabling detailed radiation simulations. Focusing on urban canyons with tree canopies the model computes shortwave and longwave radiation interactions for each tree, building and terrain voxel. Tower meteorological data from Basel, Switzerland, drives the model to simulate radiation conditions at street level. Model accuracy is evaluated using 4-component net radiometers placed within (2 m height) and over (40 m height) a street canyon.

These results show the model's potential to advance urban ecophysiology research, particularly in understanding tree-urban interactions and energy balance. This work aims to offer a computationally efficient tool for studying vegetated versus non-vegetated urban areas, supporting climate-resilient urban design.

Assessing the role of herbaceous plant species in particulate matter capture and accumulation: a case study from Small Nature-Based Solutions in the Metropolitan area of Milan (Italy)

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Abstract

Urban vegetation significantly contributes to air pollution mitigation by capturing and accumulating particulate matter (PM). While most research has focused on woody species (i.e., trees and shrubs), the potential of herbaceous species remains understudied. Herbaceous plants represent a promising alternative to the exclusive employment of woody or shrub species for nature-based solutions due to fewer physical constraints in urban environments, including shallow rooting depth and minimal canopy height. This is especially relevant in areas where the structure of the urban fabric does not allow for ample subterranean or subaerial soil volumes.

This study investigates the efficiency of six common herbaceous species commonly used in urban landscapes (i.e., *Eriocapitella hupehensis*, *Geranium sanguineum*, *Nepeta × faassenii*, *Nassella tenuissima*, *Panicum virgatum* and *Calamagrostis arundinacea*), in capturing different PM fractions within a newly implemented small nature-based solution in the metropolitan area of Milan. Microscopic leaf-surface characteristics, known to influence PM capture efficiency, were analyzed for each species. A gravimetric method was employed for PM quantification, with protocol adjustments made to accommodate the unique morphological traits of herbaceous species. The findings provide new insights on the role of herbaceous vegetation in enhancing urban air quality and offer guidance for integrating these species into future urban greening initiatives.

Strategy for Addressing the Impact of Climate Change on Ecosystem Service Interactions in the Management of Forest Resources in Belgrade

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Abstract

Forest and forest land ecosystem services are of immense importance for the city of Belgrade. However, ecosystem degradation leads to irreversible loss of functions and services, which ultimately compromises human well-being. Evaluating ecosystem services, including their economic valuation, supports decision-making processes and involves local communities and stakeholders.

This strategy assesses the vulnerability and resilience of forests in Belgrade and their potential for adaptation to climate change by developing climate models incorporating varying greenhouse gas concentration scenarios.

Key challenges identified include the adverse effects of climate change, population growth, increased demand for food and energy, and urban sprawl, all of which collectively threaten natural resources and biodiversity.

Based on research into the ecosystem services of forests and forest ecosystems in Belgrade, as well as the impacts of various climate change scenarios, goals were set for 2050, with impact projections through 2100. The findings indicate substantial transformations in forest stand composition, including the local extinction of numerous species and the colonization of habitats by predominantly invasive species. This document proposes a model for identifying and evaluating ecosystem services and analyzing their temporal changes due to the persistent effects of climate change, particularly global atmospheric warming.

A participatory approach was employed in the strategy's development, involving public engagement through surveys, interviews (one semi-structured interview), and workshops (seven conducted using focus group methodologies and one utilizing the Delphi technique). This process resulted in the formulation of 10 specific objectives with a total of 70 measures and activities designed for implementation by 2030.

The strategy was formally adopted by the Belgrade City Assembly on December 26, 2022, and published in the Official Gazette No. 112/22.

Monitoring climate-fit, low-cost urban mini forests in Eastern Austria

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Abstract

Green spaces and trees fulfil a wide range of socio-economic and ecological functions in urban areas. These include influencing the microclimate, reducing noise and dust, regulating water and material flows and providing habitat and food source for animals. Plantings often consist of only one species or one variety, and the trees planted are several metres high, making them susceptible to transplant shock. A further challenge is that, due to drastic climate change, the traditional species and varieties planted today may not necessarily be suitable for the future. In response, we launched the URMNI project in 2024 to evaluate the use of a range of potentially climate-fit tree species as an alternative to the traditional, costly and sometimes unsustainable approach to green space management. On the one hand, the planting follows established forestry concepts: the trees and shrubs are planted young, bare-rooted, in a mixed stand, close together. The design aims to create more resilient, diverse and self-developing island-like ecosystems in a short period of time. This is important in urban areas where space is limited, growing conditions are extreme and there is a need for diverse, less vulnerable ecosystems. In times of extreme climatic conditions, urban mini forests are expected to offer advantages over the traditional single-tree plantings. URMINI will monitor the growth and survival of woody plants and how they affect fauna, flora and microclimate, as well as their potential for sequestering carbon. In addition, URMINI forests will be designed and communicated in a way that is aesthetically pleasing to the local community. Community responses are documented throughout the process. Our presentation will outline the methods, design and layout of the URMINI forests and present the preliminary results of the project.

Long-term ecological monitoring of city trees as tool in urban transformation towards Blue-Green infrastructure

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Abstract

As climate change continues, heatwaves and droughts are becoming more frequent and prolonged, challenging urban systems. Urban systems are built by and home to people, but they are also home to many other forms of life such as plants and animals. They include buildings and roads, but also green spaces and water management. To make urban areas resilient and livable for all in the future, we need new approaches and ideas to tackle the consequences of climate extremes such as flooding and overheating. Green spaces in particular have the potential to partially mitigate climate extremes in cities; trees cool sealed infrastructure in the summer. As part of the Urban Transformation - Towards Blue-Green Infrastructure (UT-UBGI) as well as the CoolTree project, we are generating real field data from established urban green spaces. Focusing on urban trees, we assess their health, sap flow, radial growth, fine root growth, microhabitats, tree microclimate and cooling effect on their surroundings. The tree monitoring, we present was started in early 2025 and will cover at least one growing season. It involves 45 trees of three different tree species located on research and university campuses of two different German cities Leipzig (UFZ) and Karlsruhe (KIT). We are covering two different experimental approaches with one observing the tree cooling and growth of *Platanus x hispanica* in parklike conditions and the second covering the physiology and cooling capacity of building and street trees of the species *Robinia pseudoacacia* and *Tilia cordata* under different irrigation regimes. The application of these irrigation schemes will show the value of investing water for already established urban trees. Finally, and overall, we aim to determine whether irrigated urban trees are healthier and cool their surroundings more effectively than their non-irrigated neighbors.

Exploring Constraints to Psychological Restoration in Green Spaces: An Inductive Approach

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Abstract

This study investigates the constraints affecting psychological restoration in public green spaces, aiming to inform future research and urban planning strategies. Grounded in the Attention Restoration Theory (ART), our research addresses the gap in understanding constraints to restoration experiences. Drawing on insights from leisure literature and affordances theory, we examine the interplay between personal and environmental factors influencing restoration outcomes.

Using an open-ended survey approach, we collected data from 1202 respondents regarding constraints encountered during outdoor restoration activities in their daily environment. Analysis revealed a diverse array of constraints, including biophysical factors, conflicting uses, and intrapersonal distractions. Key findings highlight the significance of noise pollution and crowdedness as prevalent constraints, underscoring the need for attention to these factors in both research and design interventions. Additionally, constraints related to conflicting uses and interpersonal dynamics underscore the complexity of human-environment interactions in restoration contexts.

Our study contributes to advancing understanding of constraints to restoration experiences and emphasizes the importance of considering both demand-side and supply-side factors in planning and design interventions. By recognizing the multifaceted nature of restoration constraints, we provide valuable insights for policymakers, planners, and designers seeking to enhance the restorative potential of public green spaces.

Reassessment of human green exposure in urban area from a quality perspective

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Abstract

The increase in green exposure can effectively alleviate the physical and mental health pressures faced by residents during urban development. Notably, its modification of urban microclimates significantly enhances the comfort of human settlements. However, traditional assessment systems that focus solely on "greenery ratios" overlook the critical role of vegetation quality in green exposure. When vegetation quality is compromised, ecological services cannot be delivered sustainably. This study redefines urban greening through a population-centered, quality-equity perspective. By integrating demographic and vegetation dynamics, we mapped human green exposure at the urban scale across 193 global capitals. We combined sub-city-level population data with physiological trait indicators of vegetation quality—including chlorophyll content and canopy water content—to assess dynamic changes in residents' exposure to green space quality. Key findings address: Whether vegetation quality evolves proportionally with quantity during urban development; The existence of a "green mirage"—visible vegetation growth accompanied by functional decline; Whether these trends persist across cities and neighborhoods of varying development levels, income tiers, and population scales. This work shifts urban greening paradigms from measuring mere quantity to holistically evaluating vegetation quality's human impacts. By revealing hidden inequities in plant-derived health benefits, we provide diagnostic tools to align greening policies with human needs, establishing a foundation for exploring human-vegetation interdependencies in global urban environments.

Balancing the carbon storage of Leipzig's floodplain forest with regard to the city's contribution to climate protection

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Abstract

The role of trees and forest ecosystems in overcoming the global climate crisis is discussed in numerous scientific publications and in a wide variety of media. The question arises as to what contribution forest ecosystems can make to mitigating the effects of advancing climate change, particularly in an urban context.

Hardwood floodplain forests are species-rich and highly endangered habitats that can provide many functions and ecosystem services. Due to their high storage capacity, they appear to play an important role in the global carbon cycle. The carbon stock and CO₂ sequestration potential is also an important parameter for describing the state of an ecosystem and is increasingly attracting the interest of cities. Leipzig's floodplain forest, together with its small rivers, represents the city's blue-green infrastructure. This urban floodplain landscape is categorised as important in Central Europe. Unfortunately, it is also currently struggling with a number of calamities.

Within the Lebendige Luppe project, two comparative inventories of trees and deadwood were carried out on 60 plots between 2013 and 2021. More than 8,000 individual trees of more than 20 different woody plant species were approached and the diameter at breast height and total height were measured. From this, carbon content was derived by using allometric equations and biomass expansion factors. Additionally soil profiles were sampled horizontally and analysed in the laboratory on a total of 52 plots. Dendrometer measurements were carried out and core data used to estimate the increment. In addition, the results were compared with the forestry databases in order to estimate the C-sink potential. The city of Leipzig is very interested in the results of a carbon balance and in the question of what the Leipzig floodplain forest is capable of saving in terms of CO₂ under which conditions with regard to climate protection. This study provides some answers.

Extended Root Space for Urban Trees: Importance and Monitoring

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Abstract

Urban trees are essential for the quality of life, microclimate, and biodiversity in cities. The cherry blossom avenue of Bertastrasse in Zurich exemplifies the successful integration of green spaces into urban environments, reflecting the 20th-century trend of enhancing cities through thoughtful planting. It demonstrates how well-planned greenery can complement historical architecture while providing ecological and social benefits.

However, the growth of these trees is often limited by restricted root space, affecting their resilience to environmental stress such as heat, drought, and soil compaction. The research project “Buildable Urban Tree Substrates,” conducted by ZHAW in cooperation with Grün Stadt Zürich, investigates how innovative substrate solutions and extended root spaces can improve the vitality and longevity of urban trees. In densely built environments, structural measures are necessary to ensure adequate root space despite limited land availability.

To comprehensively assess tree health and development, the project employs various monitoring methods: sensors continuously measure parameters such as soil moisture, and temperature, while visual assessments document tree vitality and growth dynamics. Various measurement methods will be presented to support research for the practical management of urban green spaces. The results will be presented and offer insights for professionals interested in sustainable urban greening with trees.

Promoting genetic and species tree diversity in landscape architecture

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Abstract

Decreasing species and genetic diversity is one of the biggest challenges affecting the resilience of urban trees and forestry to threats such as pests and diseases, climate change, and loss of urban soils. Reasons for this are the practices in the horticultural industry, a preference for few tree species and often species-poor designs among landscape architects, and the restrictions on the use of nonnative trees for nature conservation reasons.

In this presentation we introduce the “ecology and planting design” research group at the landscape architecture school in Rapperswil (OST Ostschweizer Fachhochschule). Our team brings together conservationists and urban ecologists with horticulturalists, planting designers and landscape architects. We believe that biological diversity is central to the resilience of urban trees and advocate for more species and genetic diversity through innovative solutions at the intersections of design, ecology and arboriculture. We illustrate our work through these three lines of innovation:

- 1) We reconnect biodiversity conservation and horticulture by demonstrating how urban tree collections can help to substantially increase the capacity for ex situ rare tree conservation – whether in the native or nonnative biogeographic range (Ismail et al., *Gartenpraxis* 09/2022: 24-29). In this project we also collaborate with geneticists and phytopathologists to evaluate the positive effects of genetic diversity on urban tree resilience against pests and diseases.
- 2) We experiment with climate-fit trees, Miyawaki-forest design, and the maintenance of dying alley trees on our campus in Rapperswil (near Zurich) which we use as a realworld laboratory for teaching and research (<https://www.ost.ch/de/projekt/freiraumlabor>).
- 3) We present recently implemented planting designs in Switzerland and Germany planned by our team that demonstrate the aesthetic value of a high tree species diversity in landscape architectural design.

Urban Forestry Network: Harmonizing urban forest management across Europe by bringing science to stakeholders

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Abstract

Urban forests are increasingly valued for their vital contributions to climate resilience, biodiversity, public health, and urban livability. Yet, across Europe, their governance remains fragmented, limiting their potential as multifunctional green infrastructure. The COST Action CA23148 "Urban Forestry Network" responds to this challenge by fostering a transdisciplinary, cross-sectoral research and innovation network focused on an integrative approach to urban forestry.

This Action brings together researchers, urban planners, policymakers, municipalities, civil society, and private stakeholders to bridge science, policy, and practice. Central to this effort is the development of the Urban Forest Index—a harmonized, pan-European dashboarding tool designed to monitor the performance and ecosystem service delivery of urban forests. The Index aims to support communication, decision-making, and governance by providing accessible, comparable data for a diverse range of stakeholders. It will enable cities to assess and improve the multifunctionality of their urban forests, align local practices with broader sustainability goals, and inform evidence-based management in a consistent way across different European contexts.

To inform the creation of this tool, the Urban Forestry Network has issued a call for Urban Forest Management Plans (UFMPs), Municipalities across Europe are invited to submit their management plans for inclusion in a comparative meta-analysis. This initiative will identify common challenges, best practices, and innovative approaches to urban forestry, feeding into the development of the Urban Forest Index and advancing collective knowledge for more sustainable and resilient cities.

The Urban Tree Growth Response to Climate Change

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Abstract

We investigate the growth response of urban trees to extreme heat and drought events in the Upper Rhine Valley of Germany. We aim to help urban foresters better predict how different tree species in different sites will fare in the next few decades. We also hope to identify appropriate adaptations to make their urban forests more resilient to climate disturbances (e.g., which species are performing better than others, which site alterations might be most effective). One of our main research questions is currently, "Is there more variation in urban tree growth response to climate shocks based on inherent characteristics (e.g., species) or environmental/site characteristics (e.g., soils, nearby trees/buildings)?"

To accomplish this, we have collected three increment cores (each 15-38 cm long) from each of 600 trees of 12 species. Trees are located in 3 site types (streets, parks, and forests) in Freiburg and Karlsruhe. We also collected over 450 corresponding soil samples, as well as measured dozens of site, crown, and other metrics on each tree, . This specific project (Work Package "TreeCare") is undertaken as a part of the URBORETUM project cluster, funded by the BMBF REGULUS funding package.

I document how we accomplished all fieldwork with zero direct carbon emissions (i.e., through train and bikes only), and recommends how other projects could achieve this in a streamlined way. I also provide a broader overview of identified methods for modeling urban tree growth and mortality, each one's (dis)advantages, and recent developments in this field. In particular, I would like to highlight recent studies in the US that have used long-term scientific re-measurement and archival inventory analysis to build (at relatively low cost and without additional injury to urban trees) toward more powerful, comprehensive models of urban tree growth and mortality.

Urban Forest Strategies (UFS) through the lens of climate resilience: a systematic policy review.

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Abstract

Urban forests are acknowledged for the important role they play as a nature-based solution to the impacts of climate change, providing they are well managed. Urban Forest Strategies (UFS) serve as important documents to guide better urban tree management. However, only 41% of U.K. local authorities have a publicly available strategy, with siloed working practices and resource constraints preventing uptake. Similarly, UFS can vary based on spatial, temporal, and governance factors, with most performance indicators failing to consider climate change. This is a missed opportunity to maximise the climate benefits offered by urban trees. Using qualitative data analysis software and the Eight Step Pedagogy (N7 + 1), this research aims to analyse current policies at local, regional, national, and international levels to identify correlations between governance and climate-related performance indicators and to analyse UFS content. This method provides an auditable footprint and allows effective reproducibility of further research in a rapidly changing political landscape. The research serves as a comprehensive resource for researchers and urban forest practitioners in designing more climate-resilient UFS and to inform decision-making in a range of governance structures.

Urban Labor-a-Tree: a treescape board game for participatory visioning

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Abstract

Urban treescapes hold immense cultural and social significance while remaining important in meeting net-zero targets and conserving biodiversity. Yet, underserved urban areas typically have lower tree cover, which has been linked to lower educational attainment, health and social cohesion. To address knowledge, perception and quality barriers to engaging with greenspaces, it has been recommended that communities participate in their design. More engaged communities support more resilient and sustainable future treescapes. In our recent research in the Future of UK Treescapes Branching Out project, stakeholders highlighted inequalities in accessing treescapes, but struggled to determine what practical actions to take to achieve their ideal future treescapes. We propose that being able to experiment with configurations of the treescape in a board game will help stakeholders explore actionable steps into the future and negotiate competing agendas in a neutral setting.

Blending environmental science and applied game design, our board game Urban Labor-a-tree invites players to collaborate to design treescapes that meet multiple societal and ecological goals. Our objective for the game is to extract the core components of social-ecological interactions within a treescape into playable and fun game mechanics that allow players to choose what types of trees to plant where (e.g. parks, streets, homes) and help them grow while exploring the benefits, and costs they can have over a period of time. The intention is to enhance public participation and engagement in understanding urban treescapes and foster stronger community connections to trees.

For our contribution, we propose a play session to demonstrate the game with some time to gather attendees' reflections and present our own initial evaluation of the potential of board games as tactile, interactive and immersive means of engaging communities in tree conservation and prompting shared learning.

Building the foundations - Information Champain sensitizing for services and needs of Urban Forestry

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Abstract

Urban trees play a crucial role in mitigating heat, managing rainwater, improving air quality, and enhancing overall urban ecology, directly contributing to human health and well-being. Despite their importance, awareness of their benefits remains limited amongst city inhabitants and users. This project aims to engage both children and adults by providing accessible, target-group-specific information on urban trees and their ecosystem services.

To achieve this, an interactive information system has been developed, featuring child-friendly comic-style information boards, school worksheets (primary school level), and digital fact sheets accessible via QR codes. The information boards are being strategically placed in various locations—schools, public spaces, residential areas, and commercial complexes—forming an educational trail suitable for outdoor learning within the framework of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD).

In the first phase, twelve differently themed information boards, worksheets, and fact sheets were created. Several trails have been installed or are planned to be installed in different cities in Switzerland.

A dedicated website has been launched, offering centralized access to all materials and an interactive map displaying the board locations. The project will also be introduced to teaching staff to encourage wider adoption in educational settings.

By fostering awareness through engaging and easily accessible information, this initiative aims to strengthen public appreciation for urban forestry and its essential role in creating resilient, livable cities.

Addressing equity in the Forestami project: accessibility, distribution, and engagement in urban green spaces

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Abstract

Dense urban contexts are under pressure due to the constant population growth and an urban development model oriented towards soil consumption and sealing. In this scenario, urban voids become opportunities to imagine a new landscape in which nature represents the tool to contrast climate change, improve citizens' health, and strengthen the sense of community.

In this direction, Forestami works in one of the densest European metropolis, the Milan Metropolitan Area (MMA), structuring an urban forestry project that embraces the challenges of developing a new form of regeneration within the urban and peri-urban development and promoting a fair and just transition. Forestami works towards the direction of equity by studying the accessibility of urban green spaces and identifying the less served parts of the territory, realising new natural spaces distributed in the entire metropolitan territory, engaging citizens in various activities, and promoting a new shared tool for green management.

The planting sites are selected mainly considering their environmental, ecological, and cultural qualities, thus guaranteeing the availability and accessibility of green spaces even to marginal territories and administrations with fewer resources. By enhancing a spontaneous landscape, Forestami promotes the role of informal green spaces in guaranteeing spatial and environmental justice.

In this process, Forestami involves citizens, students, families, local communities, and vulnerable subjects who become an active part of the tree planting process, directly participating in the promotion of the project and the sustainable development of the territory.

Finally, Forestami is developing a platform to collect planting data, creating a systematised database of metropolitan planting activities. This tool will align existing resources between the various administrations, enabling and capacitating all the municipalities to manage their natural assets in an integrated manner

Praxis Example: Biodiversity Park Bornkamp – Revitalizing a Cemetery as a Community-Driven Model for Urban Biodiversity Enhancement

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Abstract

The Biodiversity Park Bornkamp transforms a decommissioned cemetery into a multifunctional urban biodiversity hub. This 1.7-hectare initiative, led by WeField e.V. in collaboration with conservation organizations and community groups, aims to create accessible natural spaces and biodiversity islands in Hamburg Altona.

This project showcases a community-driven approach to urban biodiversity enhancement. Since the cemetery's decommissioning in 2011, its ecological and recreational potential has remained untapped. Our initiative revitalizes the space by expanding tree stands, enriching shrub diversity, and converting lawns into biodiverse ecosystems. The 17,000 m² project area, with 3,400 m² under direct transformation, demonstrates how urban green spaces can be repurposed for ecological and social benefits.

Implementation & Impact

Key partners, including the German Wildlife Foundation, NABU, Heckenretter e.V., and HafenCity University Hamburg, ensure a sustainable long-term maintenance strategy. Starting in March 2025, a micro-tree nursery will be established using locally collected seeds to foster climate-resilient trees with strong root systems, improving soil quality and aeration.

Terra Preta substrates will be applied where needed to enhance soil water retention, boost vitality, and sequester carbon. Further planting initiatives in 2025/26 will engage volunteers, schools, and kindergartens, promoting community participation and environmental education. The park will feature hedgerows, tiny forests, forest gardens, sand habitats, and wildflower meadows, reinforcing urban biodiversity and sustainable land management.

This contribution to EFUF2025 highlights practical, replicable strategies for integrating biodiversity in urban planning, emphasizing community engagement, ecosystem resilience, and multifunctional landscape design.

Assessing tree-associated biodiversity: Insights from eDNA analysis on trees growing near streets, urban parks and peri-urban forests

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Abstract

Trees are vital components of urban green infrastructure, enhancing city life while providing essential habitats that support biodiversity in cities. We used non-invasive environmental DNA (eDNA) analysis, which detects species that are visually elusive or exist at low abundance, to assess urban tree-associated biodiversity. We targeted to identify vertebrates and arthropods associated with trees by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) coupled with next-generation sequencing (NGS). The discrimination between vertebrate and invertebrate species was based on targeting distinct genetic markers, such as cytochrome oxidase subunit 1 and 16S mitochondrial rRNA.

Our study focused on five tree species—*Acer platanoides*, *Quercus rubra*, *Quercus robur*, *Robinia pseudoacacia*, and *Tilia cordata*—in Karlsruhe, Germany, between November and December 2024. eDNA samples were collected following a factorial design incorporating tree species, three habitat types (street, park, and peri-urban forest), and two tree size classes (20–50 cm and >50 cm DBH). Surface swabs were taken from four trunk sides using sterilized materials, and three samples per category were pooled, resulting in 90 composite samples.

Our analysis identified more than 40 vertebrate genera, including birds, mammals, and reptiles, along with over 250 arthropod genera, predominantly insects spanning more than 10 orders. While common urban species were detected, invasive species were also present. Insects were more abundant on street trees than in parks and peri-urban forests, whereas mammals were more frequently associated with trees in parks and peri-urban forests than street trees. Among tree species, *Robinia pseudoacacia* harbored the highest insect diversity. Future research will integrate microhabitat assessments to refine our understanding of biodiversity patterns in urban trees.

CityTree - An Interactive Tool for Calculating Growth and Ecosystem Services of the Most Common Tree Species in Central European Cities

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Abstract

In view of the urban heat island effect and climate change, the importance of green infrastructures for the cities' climate is increasing. Trees improve urban environments by providing ecosystem services (ESS) such as cooling, oxygen release, carbon storage and runoff reduction. These ESS are influenced by species, age, size, structure and vitality of the trees. The CityTree model (Rötzer et al. 2019) was developed to quantify these ESS, estimating tree growth and species-specific benefits like carbon storage, cooling and runoff based on site conditions. CityTree is a process-based model using physiological equations to calculate growth depending on environmental conditions like climate and soil characteristics. It uniquely links tree growth to the tree's water balance and ESS, including carbon fixation and cooling through transpiration. Currently, the model is parameterized for the 12 most common tree species found in Central European cities.

A basic version of the CityTree model is published as an online tool (www.zsk.tum.de) and is available to all users free of charge. The online tool has a simple and concise input mask where the variables city (currently 34 cities), species, stem diameter class (from 0 to 100 cm in 10 cm steps), soil type (sand, loamy sand, sandy loam, loam, loess and clay), soil sealing (from 0 to 100 %), sky view factor (from no horizon cover to very high horizon cover) and the time period (current climate, dry year, two climate scenarios) can be selected. After choosing the individual parameters, CityTree calculates the growth and ecosystem services carbon storage, runoff, cooling through shading and transpiration of the selected tree species. A simple click displays the input data and simulation results in a new web page and saves them in a file.

The model supports the management of urban tree stocks and supports planners and arborists in selecting and caring for trees in cities, especially in the face of climate change.

Resilient minds, resilient cities: urban forestry as a mental well-being strategy in Europe

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Abstract

As cities grow, urban forests represent an ever more vital urban planning tool for enhancing public health and community wellness. In this paper, we discuss the key contribution of urban spaces with high levels of greenness across a variety of European urban settings to reducing stress, enhancing mental health, and promoting social cohesion. By analyzing urban rewilding in Amsterdam, Netherlands, and Barcelona, Spain, in this study, it is determined that such interventions effectively counteract anxiety, enhance cognitive function, and promote social cohesion in urban citizens. Urban forests serve as mental refugia, enhancing both Attention Restoration Theory (ART) and Stress Recovery Theory (SRT), and providing mental restoration and emotional well-being for urban citizens. Beyond individual benefit, urban forests contribute towards more resilient communities through social contact and an increased environmental stewardship among citizens. Policies with 'green prescriptions', including forestry, in urban planning contribute a lot towards maximising public wellbeing and creating a deeper sense of community. By putting urban forestry first, European urban centres are creating a path towards happier, healthier, and more resilient communities. Finally, this study sheds light on the scalability of such approaches at a global level, urging a worldwide commitment towards including urban forestry in public health programs. By embracing these green interventions, urban areas can make their environments livable, supporting long-term sustainability and wellness for its residents.

The importance of tree species richness in urban green spaces: a case study of two Italian cities.

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Abstract

Urban green areas enhance biodiversity and provide essential ecosystem services, making them increasingly important in urban planning amid rapid urbanization and climate change. Historically, urban green areas were seen as biodiversity-poor environments dominated by non-native species through past biotic homogenization processes, posing a significant challenge to species conservation (Grimm et al., 2008). However, research highlights that the richness and distribution of tree species influence the ecosystem services provided by urban green spaces, such as mitigating the urban heat island effect through evapotranspiration (Wang et al., 2021). This study aims to explore the species richness of urban trees in two Italian cities, Palermo and Florence, examining various types of green spaces, including tree-lined streets, public squares and historical gardens. Particular emphasis is placed on the potential of new technologies to assess and promote biodiversity in these spaces. By applying advanced LiDAR technology, precise biometric data on tree structure and health are collected, enabling the creation of 3D tree models. The i-Tree software will be utilized to assess the ecosystem services provided by urban trees. Integrating LiDAR-derived data with the i-Tree software allows for a comprehensive evaluation of the ecosystem services urban trees offer, particularly in terms of carbon sequestration. These technological advancements allow for a deeper understanding of tree health and the ecosystem services urban forests offer. Leveraging cutting-edge technologies provides a comprehensive toolset for urban planners and environmental managers to assess and manage urban biodiversity effectively. Creating maps of tree species richness and the ecosystem services offered by these urban green areas facilitates the monitoring of future tree planting programs' effectiveness and the development of management strategies aimed at promoting greater ecological sustainability in cities.

Applying the Urban Heat Vulnerability Index to Formulate Urban Policies: A Theoretical Case Study of Yerevan

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Abstract

The Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect and its mitigation strategies are extensively studied and well-documented. However, their integration into urban development policies remains limited. Despite the widespread exposure of European cities to extreme heat stress, few have prioritized the issue by implementing UHI mitigation measures and incorporating them into policy frameworks. Existing scientific knowledge must be translated into actionable policies, requiring amendments to urban planning documents, modifications in urban management, and municipal practices. This research aims to apply the Urban Heat Vulnerability Index (UHVI) tool in the context of data scarcity and translate its insights into an evidence-based urban development policy proposal.

This research consists of 2 stages: modeling the UHVI for Yerevan and incorporating the results into theoretical amendments for local urban development documents. The UHVI modeling uses a widely accepted methodology that incorporates 3 key components: sensitivity, exposure, and adaptive capacity. The selected parameters, chosen based on data availability, include the proportion of the vulnerable population, population and building density, UHI intensity, tree canopy coverage, per capita green space availability, and accessibility to public green areas. The analysis of existing urban development policies involved reviewing previously established urban strategies, master plan, categorization of municipal services and their functions, legal frameworks, and conducting interviews with local authorities.

The UHVI analysis identified the need for interventions in 3 key areas: building codes and regulations, land use and development policies, and data collection and standardization. The specific policy recommendations vary depending on the parameters selected for UHVI modeling. While urban policies are inherently context-specific, the methodological framework is adaptable and can be applied to other cities with data deficits.

Root Cause of Resilience

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Abstract

Industrialisation and urbanisation have fundamentally reshaped human habitats, raising the question of whether our species has had sufficient time to adapt to modern environments. This potential mismatch between our evolutionary background and industrialised contemporary habitat might explain the increasing prevalence of stress-associated psychological dysfunction in the 21st-century. Reconnecting humans with natural environments could mitigate the negative impacts of urbanisation, improving overall psychological health. Previous research indicates that exposure to natural environments, compared to urban settings, improves mood and cognitive performance. However, past studies have neglected to quantify environmental attributes and have not considered a broad range of psychological measures. To address this gap, we conducted a randomised controlled trial, involving 161 participants exposed for three hours to either a coniferous forest, a deciduous or a city centre. Cognitive measures (Attention, Executive Function, Memory) and emotional response questionnaires (Profile of Mood States, Buss-Perry Aggression Questionnaire) were administered pre- and post-immersion. Total Mood Disturbance and all subfactors (Anger, Tension, Confusion, Fatigue, Vigour, Esteem-related Affect) significantly improved after forest, but not city, exposure, while no significant difference was found between the forests. No statistical difference was found for comparisons of aggression or cognitive performance between conditions. Environmental parameters related to urban conditions (higher temperatures, anthropophony, more ultrafine particles) correlated with increased negative mood, whereas natural parameters (greenness, biophony and alpha-pinene) correlated with improved mood. This study replicated the positive impact of forest environments on psychological well-being and beyond that took the first innovative steps towards identifying specific environmental drivers of these effects.

Tree Cities of the World - next steps in a national context

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Abstract

Tree Cities of the World (TCOW) is a global recognition programme to celebrate those towns and cities that are championing urban forestry, developed by the Arbor Day Foundation (USA) and UN FAO. Now in its sixth year, Trees for Cities has been leading the programme in the UK since its inception and has seen both successes and challenges in integrating the global scheme to the UK landscape in this time. 2024 saw the first gathering of recognised UK Tree Cities and following consultation exercises at this event the need to a) give greater long term strategic positioning and planning of the scheme and b) better develop the award for long time recipients became apparent. In light of these findings, and at a time where interest in urban forestry is growing in the UK, Trees for Cities will demonstrate how it is working with partners, award holders and programme leaders to develop an innovative strategic vision for TCOW in the country. Ultimately, this work aims to build ever increasing momentum behind the scheme and will show how it can be leveraged as an advocacy tool to promote and elevate the urban forest in both local and national plans. Findings on how the scheme is received by UK municipalities from the first gathering of UK Tree Cities will be shared as well as an outline of the proposed strategy to better integrate the programme in the UK and ambitions for change

European-wide surveys on skills, capacity and training needs for Urban Nature Plans

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Abstract

The European Biodiversity Strategy 2030 calls for all European cities of at least 20,000 inhabitants to develop Urban Nature Plans (UNPs) to create biodiverse, resilient and accessible greenspace networks. The Horizon Europe UNP+ Project aims to facilitate this process by working with diverse stakeholders to build capacity for effective delivery of UNPs at city level.

To inform and initiate the UNP+ Capacity Building Programme, two Europe-wide online surveys were undertaken addressing different target groups. The first survey focused on local authorities' use of existing capacity and training tools, whilst the second focused on Nature-based Solutions (NbS) designers, developers and suppliers. It aimed to explore industry's skills and needs for delivering and implementing UNPs.

Surveys were drafted by UNP+ Project partners and tested with the Project's "Lighthouse" and "Greening" Cities and selected industry partners. Following the process of refinement, surveys were distributed through multiple networks focusing on local authorities and related commercial enterprises. The surveys were designed to be engaging for stakeholders, to be complementary to existing programs and to result in the production of practical outcomes.

The surveys provided interesting results. They highlighted a lack of consistent knowledge and approach, the challenges faced by nature-based enterprises, a need for standardised, yet locally relevant tools and a requirement to focus on the advanced stages of the UNP process. This includes the mapping and modelling of biodiversity, ecosystem services and green space connectivity.

Despite widespread promotion of the surveys through diverse networks, the response rate from cities was lower than expected. This highlights the challenge of overcoming "survey fatigue" from stakeholders. It indicates a need to combine surveys where possible and to share results across various European projects to ensue effective data collection and response rates

Sustaining and expanding Wrocław's urban forest

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Abstract

The presentation will focus on the various aspects of planning and sustaining urban forest in Wrocław, Poland, introducing the city's Municipal Greenery Authority (ZZM) and the strategic and operational initiatives it has implemented to more effectively manage city's trees.

ZZM is responsible for maintaining public greenery throughout Wrocław, including parks, municipal forests, and roadside vegetation—covering approximately 10% of the city's area. Every year, thousands of trees are inspected, cared for, felled, and planted. The presentation will explore the practical aspects of growing and sustaining Wrocław's urban forest, such as survival rates, the reasons for tree removal, and figures for new plantings. It will also cover evolving standards for establishing young trees, the impact of local law on the urban forest, and related challenges.

The impact of programmes like the Participatory Budget and the Green Patronage programme, which allows donors to contribute to the city's urban forest, will also be discussed. The authority's experiences with planting different species and varieties will be explored, as well as challenges related to pests, diseases, and climate change—especially heatwaves and drought.

In relation to climate challenges, the presentation will also address the expected outcomes of the LifeCoolCity project, co-financed by the EU within the LIFE programme, in which Wrocław's City Hall is a partner and Wrocław serves as a demonstration city. The project aims to tackle environmental issues through Blue-Green Infrastructure and Nature-Based Solutions, using remote sensing and machine learning. Among other goals, it will help manage the presence, quality, and biodiversity of trees in the city. The project will provide open data on all trees in Wrocław (on public and private land) through a canopy map accessible to the city's residents. The presentation will explore how this project can help sustain the urban forest and benefit the city.

NOTES

ORGANISING COMMITTEE

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ArboCityNet
Schweizer Netzwerk für Urban Forestry

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